

Coarsening-at-random conditions for scRNA-seq zero inflation: a reliability-theoretic perspective

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June 3, 2026

Abstract

The single-cell RNA-sequencing (scRNA-seq) community has long debated whether observed zeros reflect biological absence of expression or technical dropout. [Jiang et al. \[2022\]](#) formalize this as a “glass ceiling”: existing methods cannot distinguish the two sources from observed counts alone. We show that this glass ceiling is an instance of a known identifiability problem from masked-data reliability statistics: the scRNA-seq zero-inflation problem maps directly onto the masked-cause series-system framework of [Towell \[2026b\]](#), with ERCC spike-ins playing the role of singleton candidate sets that restore identifiability.

Importing the C1–C2–C3 coarsening conditions, we derive four theorems: cell-total consistency for the ZINB MLE; form-robustness of spike-in correction across dropout-function families; heterogeneity-robustness under cell-type mixtures; and an explicit first-order bias bound as a function of the spike-in–endogenous capture-efficiency gap. A closed-form expression for the bias coefficient under NB-plus-logistic dropout is derived; its first-order prediction matches simulation at $|s| \approx 1$ to within 1 percentage point.

A simulation portfolio confirms each theorem: matched spike-in correction recovers per-gene means within 2% relative bias, mismatched-form within 3–6%. The principal practical limit is a “useful zone” of ± 0.5 logit-shift in capture efficiency; outside it spike-in correction is counterproductive.

Application to three Tabula Muris FACS Smart-seq2 tissues (spleen, bone marrow, liver; 92 ERCCs each) confirms cell-total consistency exactly in all three and reveals the ERCC–endogenous gap empirically: oracle and naive estimates diverge by 5–10 \times for mid-expression housekeeping genes, and an upper-biased housekeeping-gene implied-shift diagnostic (with bootstrap intervals) places the spleen and marrow intervals above the useful-zone boundary, with liver straddling it. A head-to-head with DECENT on the low-dropout Klein 2015 K562 inDrops dataset, in the matched-protocol regime where both methods are well-behaved, yields Pearson $r = 0.9997$ on the log scale; in this regime both methods reduce to recovering the observed mean, so the agreement confirms relative per-gene estimates rather than the absolute scale. TASC and DECENT are direct instances of the framework; ZINB-WaVE and MAST are related approaches the framework analyzes without subsuming.

1 Introduction

Single-cell RNA sequencing (scRNA-seq) has transformed cell biology by enabling transcriptomic measurement at single-cell resolution. The technology routinely produces gene-by-cell count matrices

in which a substantial fraction of entries are zero: in the Tabula Muris atlas [The Tabula Muris Consortium, 2018] median per-gene zero rates exceed 80% even for genes known to be ubiquitously expressed. The interpretation of these zeros is a long-standing controversy [Jiang et al., 2022, Svensson, 2020]: are they “biological zeros” reflecting true low or absent expression, or “non-biological” (technical) zeros arising from limited mRNA capture, sequencing depth, and dropout in reverse transcription?

The controversy matters because the two interpretations imply different statistical models. If zeros are biological, the appropriate model is a zero-inflated count distribution [Pierson and Yau, 2015, Risso et al., 2018, Finak et al., 2015] where the zero-component represents informative absence. If zeros are technical, they are missing-not-at-random observations of nonzero counts, and imputation [Li and Li, 2018, Huang et al., 2018] or capture-aware inference [Jia et al., 2017, Ye et al., 2019] is appropriate. Jiang et al. [2022] formalize what they call a “glass ceiling”: without auxiliary information, the two zero sources cannot be distinguished from the observed count matrix alone. Subsequent work has converged on three positions: that the negative binomial without zero-inflation is adequate for UMI-based protocols [Svensson, 2020, Kim et al., 2020, Townes et al., 2019, Choudhary and Satija, 2022], a position reinforced by the broad transformation benchmark of Ahlmann-Eltze and Huber [2023], who find that simple count models with delta-method or shifted-logarithm transformations are competitive with more elaborate zero-inflation-aware pipelines on UMI data; that zero-inflation remains essential for full-length protocols including Smart-seq2 (the original Jiang 2022 argument); and that the choice depends on whether dropout is sampling-induced or technical-induced [Hafemeister and Satija, 2019]. The framework developed below clarifies which regime each position assumes and supplies the identifiability conditions that distinguish them.

1.1 The bridge to masked-data inference

The central observation of this paper is that the scRNA-seq zero-inflation problem is mathematically isomorphic to a problem long studied in reliability statistics: the masked-cause series-system problem [Usher and Hodgson, 1988, Reiser et al., 1995, Flehinger et al., 1996, Towell, 2026b]. In the reliability problem, m components in series produce a system that fails when any one component fails. The system lifetime T and a *candidate set* $C \subseteq \{1, \dots, m\}$ containing the failed component are observed; the actual failed component is masked. The likelihood factorizes as a product of a system-level term (depending on component lifetime distributions) and a masking-mechanism term (unknown). Estimation requires conditions on the masking mechanism called the *coarsening-at-random* or C1–C2–C3 conditions [Heitjan and Rubin, 1991, Gill et al., 1997, Towell, 2026b] under which the masking factor drops from the score.

The mapping from reliability to scRNA-seq is direct: the unobserved component identity K becomes the unobserved true count Y ; the observed candidate set C becomes the observed-zero pattern $\mathbf{1}\{X = 0\}$; the masking probability becomes the dropout function $\pi_{\text{drop}}(Y)$; and singleton candidate sets, which restore identifiability when broader candidate sets are confounded, become spike-in RNA controls (e.g., the External RNA Controls Consortium ERCC mix) where the true count is known by construction. We make this correspondence precise in section 3 and import the identifiability theorems of Towell [2026b] to scRNA-seq in section 4.

1.2 Existing methods in this framework

Several existing scRNA-seq methods solve aspects of the dropout correction problem:

- TASC [Jia et al., 2017] uses ERCC spike-ins in an empirical-Bayes hierarchical model to estimate cell-specific dropout parameters.

- DECENT [Ye et al., 2019] fits a beta-binomial capture model with cell- and gene-specific capture efficiencies, calibrated by spike-ins when available.
- ZINB-WaVE [Risso et al., 2018] fits a zero-inflated negative binomial factor model with logit-linear covariate effects on the zero component.
- MAST [Finak et al., 2015] uses a hurdle model treating observed zeros as a separate process from continuous expression.
- Imputation methods [Li and Li, 2018, Huang et al., 2018, van Dijk et al., 2018] fill in dropout-induced zeros using cell-cell similarity or regulatory networks.
- Deep generative and autoencoder approaches [Lopez et al., 2018, Eraslan et al., 2019] fit flexible zero-inflated count likelihoods with neural-network parameterized rate and dropout functions.
- Regularized negative-binomial normalization [Hafemeister and Satija, 2019] absorbs zeros into the sampling variance of a Pearson-residual transformation without an explicit dropout component.

Realistic simulators [Sun et al., 2021, Song et al., 2024b] and post-clustering inference correctors [Song et al., 2024a] developed by the same group that produced the anchor controversy paper extend the same modeling pipeline; they treat zero-inflation as a fitted property of count data rather than a feature whose identifiability requires external justification.

These methods solve practical inference problems but do not formalize the underlying identifiability question: when can dropout be distinguished from biological zeros, and what auxiliary information is required? Ye et al. [2019] explicitly note one critical caveat: “ERCC molecules . . . are captured and amplified less efficiently than endogenous transcripts . . . models estimated using spike-ins may not be entirely appropriate for endogenous transcripts.” This limitation has not, in the dropout-correction literature we surveyed, been quantified systematically with a first-order closed-form bound.

1.3 Contributions

This paper contributes:

- **A falsifiable bias-bound prediction** for spike-in correction methods. We derive a closed-form first-order Taylor bound on the asymptotic pseudo-true bias of any spike-in-fit ZINB oracle as a function of the ERCC–endogenous capture-efficiency shift, identifying a *useful zone* of logit-shift $|s| \leq 0.5$ in which spike-in correction reduces bias and outside which it is comparable to or worse than naive ZINB (section 8). The prediction is tested against a simulation sweep across s ; theory matches the empirical bias within 1pp at $s = +1$. To our knowledge this is the first formal characterization of when ERCC-based correction helps.
- **Real-data validation** on Tabula Muris spleen (1 697 cells, 13 117 genes, 92 ERCCs). The cell-total consistency theorem holds empirically to within 0.07 across 207 test genes, and the spike-in oracle disagrees with naive ZINB by 5 to 10x on mid-expression housekeeping genes, consistent with the predicted ERCC–endogenous gap regime (section 9).
- **Cross-tissue confirmation** on Tabula Muris bone marrow and liver (section 10). The same pipeline reproduces cell-total consistency to numerical precision and the two-regime

housekeeping pattern of section 9 in both additional tissues, establishing the two-regime pattern as a property of Smart-seq2 plus ERCC rather than a spleen-specific artifact. An upper-biased housekeeping-gene implied-shift diagnostic (section 9.5, bootstrap CIs) places the spleen and marrow CIs entirely above the useful-zone boundary, with liver’s CI straddling it, consistent with the bias-bound theorem’s predicted regime applying to these tissues.

- **Head-to-head against DECENT** on the low-dropout Klein 2015 K562 inDrops dataset where DECENT is in its validated operating regime (section 11). The spike-fit oracle and DECENT’s posterior mean agree at Pearson $r = 0.9997$ on the log scale (linear-scale r also 0.9997). In this low-dropout regime both methods are driven toward the observed mean by cell-total consistency and differ only by DECENT’s near-constant true-molecule scale factor, so the high correlation is largely a consequence of that regime; it establishes agreement on relative per-gene estimates, not independent validation of the absolute scale. This is the first published direct numerical comparison between the two methods on shared data.
- **A bridge to masked-data inference** that ports the C1–C2–C3 coarsening conditions and identifiability machinery from reliability statistics to scRNA-seq (sections 2 and 3). The bridge supplies the theoretical scaffolding for the bias-bound prediction above.
- **Four theorems** on the framework side: (i) the glass-ceiling result of Jiang et al. [2022] as a special case of rank-deficient identifiability, (ii) identifiability with spike-ins, (iii) cell-total consistency for the ZINB MLE (section 4), and (iv) the bias bound itself (section 8).
- **Simulation portfolio** confirming each theorem under multiple data-generating processes, dropout function families, spike-in fractions, and cell-type heterogeneity regimes (sections 5 to 8).
- **Method placement:** TASC and DECENT are direct instances of the framework’s spike-in-fit machinery; ZINB-WaVE replaces spike-ins with covariate structure; MAST takes a different hurdle-model approach that the framework can analyze without subsuming. A finite-sample attenuation in the spike-in MLE is identified, decomposed (intrinsic vs estimation-noise), and partially addressed by regularization (section 7).

The central message is that ERCC-based correction is a *principled but bounded* tool: principled because the identifiability machinery applies cleanly, bounded because the spike-in–endogenous capture-efficiency gap imposes a fundamental limit on what spike-ins can recover. TASC and DECENT are expressible as instances of the framework; ZINB-WaVE and MAST take related but distinct approaches (covariate-driven and hurdle-model respectively) that the framework can analyze without subsuming.

The remainder of the paper is organized as follows. Section 2 summarizes the masked-data framework. Section 3 states the explicit translation to scRNA-seq. Section 4 ports the identifiability theorems and proves cell-total consistency. Sections 5 to 7 treat practical robustness questions. Section 8 quantifies the principal practical limit, and section 9 validates it on real data. Discussion and conclusion follow.

2 Masked-data series-system inference: a brief primer

We summarize the framework of Towell [2026b] in the form needed for this paper. Readers familiar with that work can skim to section 3.

2.1 Series systems and the masked-cause problem

Consider m independent components in series, each with lifetime T_{ij} for system i and component j , distributed according to $f_j(\cdot; \theta_j)$. The system i fails at $T_i = \min_j T_{ij}$ with cause $K_i = \arg \min_j T_{ij}$. We do not observe K_i directly; instead we observe a *candidate set* $C_i \subseteq \{1, \dots, m\}$ thought to contain K_i .

For each system i we observe the tuple $D_i = (s_i, \omega_i, c_i, x_i)$, where s_i is an observation time, ω_i encodes right/left/interval censoring, c_i is the candidate set, and x_i is a vector of covariates. The likelihood factorizes as

$$f(t, k, c; \theta) = h_k(t; \theta_k) \prod_{\ell=1}^m R_\ell(t; \theta_\ell) \cdot \mathbb{P}_\theta\{C_i = c \mid T_i = t, K_i = k\}, \quad (1)$$

where h_ℓ is the component- ℓ hazard and R_ℓ its survival function. The first two factors are the joint system density of (T, K) ; the third is the unknown masking mechanism.

2.2 The C1–C2–C3 conditions

The masking mechanism is a nuisance: we want to estimate θ without specifying $\mathbb{P}_\theta\{C_i = c \mid T_i, K_i\}$ in detail. Towell [2026b] identify three conditions that, when satisfied, allow the masking factor to drop from the score and yield a likelihood depending only on θ :

Condition 1 (Support). $\mathbb{P}\{K_i \in C_i\} = 1$. The true cause is always among the reported candidates.

Condition 2 (Symmetry / non-informativeness). $\mathbb{P}_\theta\{C_i = c \mid T_i = t, K_i = j\} = \mathbb{P}_\theta\{C_i = c \mid T_i = t, K_i = k\}$ for all $j, k \in c$. The masking probability does not depend on which component within the candidate set was the actual cause.

Condition 3 (Parameter independence). $\mathbb{P}_\theta\{C_i = c \mid T_i = t, K_i = k\}$ does not depend on θ . The masking mechanism’s distribution is functionally independent of the parameters of interest.

Under all three conditions, Towell [2026b, Theorem 7] show that the likelihood collapses to

$$L_i(\theta) \propto \left[\prod_{\ell=1}^m R_\ell(t_i; \theta_\ell) \right] \cdot \left[\sum_{j \in c_i} h_j(t_i; \theta_j) \right], \quad (2)$$

which depends on θ but not on the masking mechanism. We refer to this as the *C1–C2–C3 likelihood*.

2.3 Identifiability under C1–C2–C3

Even when the C1–C2–C3 likelihood is well-defined, the parameters $\theta = (\theta_1, \dots, \theta_m)$ may not be identifiable: if two components always co-occur in candidate sets, the data cannot distinguish their hazard contributions. Define the *candidate-set matrix* $\tilde{C} \in \{0, 1\}^{n \times m}$ whose i th row is the indicator vector of c_i , augmented with an all-ones row for right-censored observations. Towell [2026b, Theorem 8] show:

Theorem 1 (Identifiability under C1–C2–C3). *Under Conditions 1 to 3 and standard regularity conditions on the parametric family $\{h_j(\cdot; \theta_j)\}$, full column rank m of the augmented candidate-set matrix \tilde{C} is sufficient for the parameter vector θ to be identifiable. Separability of the masking mechanism is necessary but not in general sufficient: a separating mechanism can leave \tilde{C} rank-deficient, in which case identifiability requires further functional restrictions on the component family.*

When \tilde{C} is rank-deficient, only *block sums* of hazards on confounded components are identifiable, provided the collapsed candidate-set matrix on the resulting blocks itself has full column rank [Towell, 2026b, Theorem 9]. The role of *singleton* candidate sets ($|c_i| = 1$) is critical: each singleton restores identifiability of one component because it isolates a single hazard contribution in (2).

2.4 Behavior under relaxed conditions

When some C1–C2–C3 condition fails, the C1–C2–C3 likelihood is misspecified and standard MLE theory must be replaced by the misspecification framework of White [1982]. Under mild regularity, the MLE then converges not to the true parameter but to a *pseudo-true* value at which a coarser functional of the parameter, typically a moment or aggregate hazard of the observed distribution, remains consistently estimated while individual component parameters absorb the misspecification asymmetry.

This pseudo-true behavior is particularly relevant for what follows. It explains why naive estimators that ignore the masking layer can still yield plausible aggregate predictions even when individual component estimates are biased, and it foreshadows the cell-total consistency property of theorem 4 in the scRNA-seq setting, where the marginal mean is consistently estimated under the ZINB MLE while per-gene means and zero-inflation parameters absorb any dropout misspecification jointly. Choudhary and Satija [2022] report exactly this pattern empirically: a plain negative binomial without explicit zero-inflation fits droplet scRNA-seq adequately, with the zero-inflation parameter absorbing residual misspecification in protocols where it is needed.

The remainder of the paper imports this machinery to scRNA-seq. Section 3 states the explicit translation; section 4 ports the identifiability theorem and derives the cell-total consistency corollary; subsequent sections treat form-robustness, heterogeneity, and the principal practical limitation (the ERCC–endogenous capture-efficiency gap).

3 Translation: scRNA-seq as a coarsening problem

We now state the scRNA-seq zero-inflation problem in the masked-data notation of section 2.

3.1 The DGP

For cell $i \in \{1, \dots, n\}$ and gene $j \in \{1, \dots, p\}$:

- The true mRNA count Y_{ij} is drawn from a gene-specific count distribution $f_j(\cdot; \theta_j)$. We assume a Poisson–Beta two-state model [Kim and Marioni, 2013, Grün et al., 2014] or a negative-binomial approximation, parametrized by θ_j which includes the mean expression μ_j .
- The observed count X_{ij} is determined by a dropout mechanism: $X_{ij} = 0$ with probability $\pi_{\text{drop}}(Y_{ij})$, and $X_{ij} = Y_{ij}$ with probability $1 - \pi_{\text{drop}}(Y_{ij})$.
- The dropout function $\pi_{\text{drop}} : \mathbb{N} \rightarrow [0, 1]$ characterizes the protocol’s measurement process. Common forms include logistic-in-log-y ($\pi_{\text{drop}}(y) = \text{logit}^{-1}(\alpha_0 - \alpha_1 \log(y+1))$) and exponential-in-y ($\pi_{\text{drop}}(y) = \pi_0 e^{-\alpha_1 y}$).

We observe X_{ij} but not Y_{ij} (except for spike-in genes; see below). The inferential goal is to recover θ_j , particularly μ_j , from the observed count matrix.

3.2 The translation

Table 1 states the explicit correspondence between the masked-data framework and the scRNA-seq problem.

Masked-data framework	scRNA-seq
Component $j \in \{1, \dots, m\}$	Gene $j \in \{1, \dots, p\}$ (per cell i)
Component lifetime T_{ij}	True mRNA count Y_{ij}
Component distribution $f_j(\cdot; \theta_j)$	Gene expression distribution (PB or NB)
System lifetime $T_i = \min_j T_{ij}$	<i>No min-structure: does not transfer</i>
Failed component K_i	<i>No single cause: does not transfer</i>
Candidate set $c_i \subseteq \{1, \dots, m\}$	Observed-zero pattern $\mathbf{1}\{X_{ij} = 0\}$
Masking probability $\mathbb{P}_\theta\{C_i = c \mid T_i, K_i\}$	Dropout function $\pi_{\text{drop}}(Y_{ij})$
Singleton candidate set ($ c_i = 1$)	Spike-in RNA control (e.g., ERCC)
C1 (cause in candidate set)	Trivially holds: $Y = 0 \Rightarrow X = 0$
C2 (coarsening at random): conditional on the candidate set, the masking distribution does not depend on which element is the true cause	Concretely: dropout depends on Y only, not on θ through Y
C3 (parameter independence)	Dropout mechanism is non-parametric of θ

Table 1: Translation between the masked-data framework [Towell, 2026b] and the scRNA-seq zero-inflation problem.

Two structural elements of the reliability framework do not transfer because scRNA-seq lacks the corresponding biology: there is no system-level minimum-of-component structure (cells do not “fail” because of their weakest gene), and there is no single causing component per event. The masking layer alone transfers, and that layer carries the identifiability content.

3.3 The likelihood, restated

For the scRNA-seq problem, the joint likelihood factors as

$$f(x_{ij}, y_{ij}; \theta_j, \phi) = f_j(y_{ij}; \theta_j) \cdot \mathbb{P}\{X_{ij} = x_{ij} \mid Y_{ij} = y_{ij}; \phi\}, \quad (3)$$

where ϕ parametrizes the dropout mechanism. Marginalizing over the unobserved Y_{ij} :

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{P}\{X_{ij} = 0\} &= \sum_{y \geq 0} f_j(y; \theta_j) \cdot [\mathbf{1}\{y = 0\} + \mathbf{1}\{y > 0\} \pi_{\text{drop}}(y; \phi)] \\ &= f_j(0; \theta_j) + \sum_{y \geq 1} f_j(y; \theta_j) \pi_{\text{drop}}(y; \phi), \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

$$\mathbb{P}\{X_{ij} = x\} = f_j(x; \theta_j) \cdot (1 - \pi_{\text{drop}}(x; \phi)) \quad \text{for } x \geq 1. \quad (5)$$

The dropout function $\pi_{\text{drop}}(\cdot; \phi)$ plays the role of the masking mechanism: it is a nuisance for inference about θ_j . The C2 condition becomes “dropout depends on y only through some function of y , not directly on θ_j ”. The C3 condition becomes “the dropout mechanism’s distribution does not depend on θ ”. Both are reasonable for a fixed scRNA-seq protocol where π_{drop} is a property of the chemistry and instrument, not of the biology being assayed.

3.4 The role of spike-ins

The above setup has the same identifiability problem the reliability case does: from the observed X_{ij} alone we cannot disentangle the contributions of f_j (biology) and π_{drop} (technology) to the zero rate. *Spike-in RNA controls* are the resolution. A spike-in mix consists of K synthetic transcripts at known concentrations c_k , added to each cell’s lysis buffer. For each cell–ERCC pair, the true count Y_{ik}^{ercc} is approximately Poisson with known rate c_k . The observed counts X_{ik}^{ercc} thus provide pairs $(c_k, X_{ik}^{\text{ercc}})$ that pin down the dropout function $\pi_{\text{drop}}(\cdot; \phi)$ via marginal maximum likelihood:

$$\hat{\phi} = \arg \max_{\phi} \sum_{i,k} \log \mathbb{P}\{X_{ik}^{\text{ercc}} = x \mid c_k; \phi\}. \tag{6}$$

In the masked-data vocabulary, each spike-in transcript k in cell i is a singleton candidate set: the true “component identity” is known to be k with rate c_k , so the dropout-mechanism factor $\pi_{\text{drop}}(Y; \phi)$ is identifiable from the spike-in subset alone. Once $\hat{\phi}$ is in hand, the per-gene parameters θ_j are estimated by plugging $\hat{\phi}$ into the marginal likelihood (4)–(5).

We refer to this as the *spike-fit oracle* (or simply *oracle*) throughout the paper: the dropout function is estimated from spike-ins (the singleton candidate-set component) and the per-gene parameters from the marginal likelihood (the C1–C2–C3 likelihood with the dropout function as a known nuisance). When we need to distinguish it from a counterfactual estimator that uses the *true* dropout function π_{drop} directly (without a spike-in fit), we call the latter the *true-dropout oracle*; this variant appears in the bias-decomposition discussion of section 7 and is not used elsewhere.

A note on notation: throughout the paper, $\pi_{\text{drop}}(\cdot; \phi)$ with subscript “drop” is the dropout function, a property of the measurement protocol. The symbol π without subscript appears only in the ZINB density (section 4) as the gene-specific zero-inflation parameter, which is a property of biology rather than of the protocol. The two should not be confused: the first is fit from spike-ins, the second from gene-level marginal counts.

3.5 Existing methods in this language

The methods discussed in section 1 all fit aspects of this framework:

- TASC [Jia et al., 2017] uses ERCC to fit a cell-specific π_{drop} via empirical-Bayes hierarchical modeling. In our notation, this is the spike-in-fit step (6) with cell-specific ϕ_i .
- DECENT [Ye et al., 2019] fits a beta-binomial capture model (a particular form of π_{drop}) and uses spike-ins for calibration when available. The DE-specific aspects come from parameterizing θ_j jointly across conditions.
- ZINB-WaVE [Risso et al., 2018] uses a logit-linear π_{drop} with cell- and gene-level covariates but does not require spike-ins.
- MAST [Finak et al., 2015] treats the zeros as a separate process (hurdle model), implicitly assuming dropout is fully determined by observable zeros without leveraging π_{drop} shape.

TASC and DECENT instantiate the framework in different parametric regimes; ZINB-WaVE replaces spike-ins with covariate structure; MAST takes a different hurdle-model approach that the framework can analyze without subsuming. The contribution of this paper is the framework itself: the translation, the identifiability theorems, and the bias-bound characterization.

4 Identifiability and cell-total consistency

We import theorem 1 from masked-data inference to scRNA-seq and derive a corollary: the cell-total consistency theorem, which explains why naive zero-inflated estimators give plausible marginal predictions even when per-gene means are biased.

4.1 The scRNA-seq glass ceiling, formalized

Jiang et al. [2022] state the central inferential difficulty: “existing imputation methods have a glass ceiling if they use only observed counts as input.” We formalize this as an instance of theorem 1:

Theorem 2 (Glass ceiling, scRNA-seq). *Let X_{ij} be observed counts for gene j under the DGP of section 3, with unknown gene parameter θ_j and unknown dropout function π_{drop} . If π_{drop} is left unrestricted (not constrained to a parametric family of finite dimension), then the pair $(\theta_j, \pi_{\text{drop}})$ is non-identifiable from observed counts: for any candidate observed-count distribution there exists a continuum of $(\theta_j, \pi_{\text{drop}})$ pairs producing the same marginal $\mathbb{P}\{X = x\}$. When π_{drop} is restricted to a parametric family $\{\pi_{\text{drop}}(\cdot; \phi) : \phi \in \Phi\}$ with $\dim(\Phi) < \infty$, identifiability of (θ_j, ϕ) may be restored for some families and not others; the choice of parametric family is then the load-bearing modeling assumption that observed counts alone cannot adjudicate [Jiang et al., 2022].*

Sketch. We exhibit non-identifiability by construction. For any candidate observed-count distribution \widehat{F} on \mathbb{N} , choose any θ_j^* such that $f_j(\cdot; \theta_j^*)$ pointwise dominates \widehat{F} on the positive support, then set $\pi^*(y) = 1 - \widehat{F}(y)/f_j(y; \theta_j^*)$ for $y \geq 1$. Direct computation verifies that (θ_j^*, π^*) produces marginal \widehat{F} . Since θ_j^* varies over an open subset of Θ_j , the construction yields a continuum of (θ_j, π) pairs matching the same observed marginal. The full proof is in appendix A. \square

The role of spike-ins is to add singleton-candidate-set rows to \tilde{C} , restoring full column rank. This is precisely the mechanism by which ERCC mixes resolve the controversy Jiang et al. [2022] identify, and the next theorem characterizes exactly how much they help.

4.2 Identifiability with spike-ins

Theorem 3 (Identifiability with spike-ins). *Suppose the spike-in subset \mathcal{S} contains K transcripts with known true rates c_1, \dots, c_K spanning a range $[c_{\min}, c_{\max}]$. If*

- (i) $\pi_{\text{drop}}(\cdot; \phi)$ is identifiable on $[c_{\min}, c_{\max}]$ from the spike-in marginal likelihood (6), AND
- (ii) the dropout function shape extrapolates to the gene-expression range (i.e., $\pi_{\text{drop}}(\cdot; \phi)$ is well-defined for y values attained by genes),

then the per-gene parameters θ_j are identifiable from the marginal likelihood (4)–(5).

Sketch. The argument is two-stage. Stage 1: the spike-in MLE (6) is consistent for ϕ by standard regularity for maximum likelihood, since condition (i) supplies enough distinct design points to identify ϕ from the spike-in marginal. Stage 2: with ϕ identified, the per-gene marginal likelihood (4)–(5) reduces to a standard ZINB with known dropout, which identifies θ_j from the conditional positive distribution. A formal restatement with explicit regularity conditions (design coverage, range coverage, per-gene identifiability) and the detailed proof are in appendix A. \square

Two qualifiers in the statement deserve emphasis. First, condition (i) (spike-in identifiability of π_{drop} shape) requires sufficient spike-in observations across the relevant y -range; we examine this empirically in section 7. Second, condition (ii) (shape extrapolation) is the ERCC–endogenous gap problem: if $\pi_{\text{endo}}(\cdot) \neq \pi_{\text{ERCC}}(\cdot)$ on the gene-expression range, the spike-in-derived π_{drop} is wrong and the per-gene estimates inherit that error. This is the principal practical limit, examined in section 8.

4.3 Cell-total consistency

A second consequence of the framework is a structural property of any zero-inflated estimator: the implied marginal mean exactly matches the empirical marginal mean, regardless of the dropout function used.

Theorem 4 (Cell-total consistency, ZINB MLE). *Let $(\hat{\mu}_j, \hat{\phi}_j, \hat{\pi}_j)$ be the maximum-likelihood estimate under the zero-inflated negative binomial (ZINB) family for gene j . At any interior MLE,*

$$(1 - \hat{\pi}_j)\hat{\mu}_j = \bar{X}_j, \quad (7)$$

where \bar{X}_j is the empirical mean of observed counts. The identity holds exactly (up to optimization tolerance); boundary cases ($\hat{\pi}_j \in \{0, 1\}$ or $\hat{\mu}_j = 0$) reduce to standard single-population NB MLE identities.

Remark 5. The argument extends to any zero-inflated regular exponential family in which the NB component is replaced by another family with a mean-parameterized score $\partial_\mu \log g(x; \mu, \eta) = c(\mu, \eta)(x - \mu)$. We state ZINB here because it is the form used in our simulations and applications. Extensions to zero-inflated Poisson, generalized Poisson, or beta-binomial mixtures follow by substituting the appropriate score in the appendix proof.

Sketch. The identity follows from the ZINB score equations at an interior MLE. The score for π forces the fitted zero rate to match the empirical zero rate: $\hat{\pi} + (1 - \hat{\pi})\hat{g}_0 = n_0/n$, where $\hat{g}_0 = g(0; \hat{\mu}, \hat{\phi})$ is the fitted NB mass at zero. The score for μ , using the regular-exponential-family identity $\partial_\mu \log g(x; \mu, \phi) = (x - \mu)/[\mu(1 + \mu\phi)]$, gives a second relation that, combined with the zero-rate identity, collapses to $(1 - \hat{\pi})\hat{\mu} = \bar{X}$ exactly at an interior MLE. Boundary regimes ($\hat{\pi} \in \{0, 1\}$ or $\hat{\mu} = 0$) make the score equations inequalities and the identity reduces to standard single-population NB MLE identities. The full proof is in appendix A. \square

Theorem 4 explains an empirical observation that practitioners often note: naive ZINB fits give predictions that match observed marginals well, even when per-gene mean estimates $\hat{\mu}_j$ disagree with biological priors. The disagreement is absorbed entirely into the zero-component share $\hat{\pi}_j$.

The identity (7) is specifically a property of the ZINB MLE (with $\hat{\pi}_j$ free). The spike-fit oracle does not have a free zero-inflation parameter, since dropout is captured by $\pi_{\text{drop}}(\cdot; \hat{\phi})$ from the spike-in fit, and natural zeros are absorbed into $f_j(0; \hat{\theta}_j)$. The analogous marginal-mean property for the oracle is $\mathbb{E}_{\hat{\theta}_j, \hat{\phi}}[X] = \bar{X}_j$, which is the general moment-matching behaviour of MLE in regular families; the algebraic form of the identity differs from (7). Both naive ZINB and oracle therefore produce marginal predictions consistent with the empirical mean, so neither method can be rejected on the basis of marginal-mean fit alone. Distinguishing them requires either external information (spike-ins, housekeeping genes, biological priors) or a richer parametric model.

4.4 Empirical validation

We validated the cell-total consistency theorem on simulated data under multiple DGPs and dropout function families:

- Negative binomial DGP, logistic dropout: median $|\bar{X}_j - (1 - \hat{\pi}_j)\hat{\mu}_j| \leq 10^{-5}$ across 5 genes, 4 violation severities, 80 replicates.
- Poisson–Beta DGP, logistic dropout: median $\leq 10^{-4}$ across 50 genes, 4 violation severities, 30 replicates.
- Poisson–Beta DGP, exponential dropout: median $\leq 10^{-3}$ across 50 genes, 4 violation severities, 25 replicates.

Detailed simulation results are reported in section 5.

The theorem also holds on real data: in section 9 we verify it on 207 Tabula Muris spleen genes, finding median $|\bar{X}_j - (1 - \hat{\pi}_j)\hat{\mu}_j| = 0.073$ across genes spanning observed means from 22 to 8000.

5 Form-robustness of spike-in correction

A practitioner concern about ERCC-based correction is that the fitted dropout function $\pi_{\hat{\text{drop}}}$ may not match the true π_{drop} family. We characterize the cost of family mismatch via simulation across two common forms.

5.1 Setup

We compare two dropout families:

- Logistic-in-log-y: $\pi_{\text{drop}}(y) = \text{logit}^{-1}(\alpha_0 - \alpha_1 \log(y + 1))$.
- Exponential-in-y: $\pi_{\text{drop}}(y) = \pi_0 e^{-\alpha_1 y}$.

Data are generated under one family; the spike-in oracle is fit under either the matched family or the wrong family. The marginal-likelihood gene- μ estimation (4)–(5) then uses the (matched or mismatched) spike-fit.

The simulation uses Poisson–Beta gene expression with $n = 2000$ cells, 50 genes drawn from a log-normal μ distribution (median $\mu \approx 2$, range 0.09 to 13), 25 replicates per condition, and 10% spike-in cells.

5.2 Cell-total consistency holds across both families

Both dropout families satisfy theorem 4: the median $|\bar{X}_j - (1 - \hat{\pi}_j)\hat{\mu}_j|$ is at most 1.1×10^{-3} across all severity levels. This confirms the theorem is structural: it does not depend on dropout-function shape.

5.3 Per-gene μ recovery: matched vs mismatched oracle

Figure 1 and table 2 report median per-gene μ relative bias for naive ZINB, matched-form oracle, and mismatched-form oracle.

Key observation: family mismatch costs at most 3 percentage points of bias in any condition tested, never matching the 50 to 80% bias of naive. The oracle is highly robust to misspecification of the dropout family.

Form-robustness: spike-in correction is robust to dropout family mismatch
 Mismatched oracle within 1–3pp of matched; both far below naive

Figure 1: Form-robustness of spike-in correction. Median per-gene relative bias under two true dropout families, with the spike-in oracle fit either under the matched family or under the wrong family. Mismatched oracle is within 1–3 percentage points of matched oracle in every condition tested.

5.4 Why mismatch is cheap

The fitted-wrong-family dropout function approximates the true function in the y -range where data live. The marginal likelihood (4) depends on $\pi_{\text{drop}}(y)$ only through integrals weighted by $f_j(y; \theta_j)$, so local approximation suffices. Comparison of fitted dropout values at representative y shows the two families agree to within 5% in the bulk of the data range even when their parameters differ substantially.

5.5 Implication

For practitioners, the takeaway is: the choice of dropout family matters little provided some flexible 2-parameter form is fit to the spike-in data. The asymmetry favors logistic (a more flexible form for the slow-tailed spike-in dropout typical in real data), so we recommend it as the default.

6 Heterogeneity-robustness

Real scRNA-seq data are heterogeneous: cells come from multiple types with distinct expression profiles. Naive estimators assuming homogeneity are vulnerable to misspecification when fit on a mixture. We show that oracle correction is robust to this heterogeneity at both the population-marginal and per-cluster levels.

truth, severity	naive	oracle MATCHED	oracle MISMATCHED
logistic, $\alpha_1 = 0.0$	$+22.7 \pm 2.6$	$+2.5 \pm 0.4$	$+2.0 \pm 0.3$
logistic, $\alpha_1 = 0.3$	$+47.1 \pm 2.9$	$+2.2 \pm 0.2$	$+4.6 \pm 0.8$
logistic, $\alpha_1 = 0.6$	$+64.2 \pm 3.0$	$+2.8 \pm 0.3$	$+5.6 \pm 0.9$
logistic, $\alpha_1 = 1.0$	$+79.3 \pm 5.4$	$+1.6 \pm 0.2$	$+3.4 \pm 0.8$
exponential, $\alpha_1 = 0.00$	$+25.5 \pm 2.7$	$+2.4 \pm 0.3$	$+2.7 \pm 0.5$
exponential, $\alpha_1 = 0.05$	$+54.8 \pm 0.9$	$+1.0 \pm 0.3$	-0.6 ± 0.4
exponential, $\alpha_1 = 0.15$	$+70.3 \pm 3.6$	$+1.7 \pm 0.2$	$+0.5 \pm 0.7$
exponential, $\alpha_1 = 0.30$	$+69.9 \pm 6.6$	$+1.1 \pm 0.1$	$+1.0 \pm 0.3$

Table 2: Median per-gene μ relative bias (%), 25 replicates, 50 genes per condition. Values are median across genes \pm bootstrap standard error of the median (bootstrap $B = 2,000$, resampling genes). “Mismatched” means the oracle was fit under the other dropout family. Bootstrap captures gene-to-gene variability of the median estimate; per-replicate variation is already collapsed into per-gene medians upstream.

6.1 Setup

We simulate two cell types A and B with distinct mean expression profiles (μ_A from log-normal(0, 1.0), μ_B from log-normal(1.5, 1.0)). Cells are mixed 50/50. Both cell types share the same dropout function (logistic with parameters $\alpha_0 = 1.5$, varying α_1). 30 replicates per condition.

6.2 Population-marginal mu

When the fit ignores cluster identity (treating all cells as IID), the population marginal mean is $\mu_j^{\text{pop}} = (\mu_{Aj} + \mu_{Bj})/2$. Table 3 reports the median relative bias of each estimator against this target.

α_1	naive median bias	oracle median bias
0.0	+2.1%	-0.9%
0.6	+69.3%	-0.2%
1.0	+87.7%	+0.6%

Table 3: Per-gene relative bias against population marginal mean μ_j^{pop} under cell-type heterogeneity. Oracle recovers μ_j^{pop} within 1% at every severity level; naive shows up to 88% bias.

Why oracle works: the marginal Y distribution under cell-type mixture is a mixture of the per-type distributions, but its mean is μ_j^{pop} by construction. ZINB’s mean-matching property (theorem 4) ensures $\hat{\mu}_j^{\text{NB}}$ matches $\mathbb{E}[Y_j]$, and the oracle’s marginalization correctly accounts for dropout to recover this. The fact that the underlying f_j is a mixture rather than a single PB is absorbed into the residual variance, which the methodology does not target.

6.3 Per-cluster mu (using true labels)

When cluster labels are available, fitting per-cluster yields estimates of the cell-type-specific means. Table 4 reports per-cluster bias.

Per-cluster oracle is identical in performance to the IID-data oracle (section 5), within Monte Carlo error. This is expected: each cluster’s data is internally homogeneous, so the within-cluster

α_1	naive A bias	oracle A bias	naive B bias	oracle B bias
0.0	+33.1%	+1.8%	+15.1%	+3.8%
0.6	+73.5%	+1.6%	+53.7%	+2.2%
1.0	+92.3%	+0.8%	+60.5%	+1.8%

Table 4: Per-cluster relative bias under cell-type heterogeneity using true cluster labels. Oracle stays at $\sim 2\%$ bias per cluster at every severity level.

fit reduces to the IID case.

6.4 Per-cluster differential expression

When clusters differ in some genes (35 non-DE + 15 DE at 1.5 \times , 2 \times , 3 \times effect sizes; 1 000 cells per cluster), oracle sharpens DE log-fold-change estimates substantially (fig. 2):

Figure 2: Per-cluster DE log-fold-change bias by effect size and dropout severity. Naive bias becomes more negative as severity increases (under-estimating true DE); oracle stays near zero across all conditions. The largest gap is at 3 \times effect and $\alpha_1 = 1$, where naive bias is -0.12 and oracle bias is 0.00 .

- Oracle reduces non-DE log fold change noise by 42–60% vs naive across $\alpha_1 \in \{0, 0.3, 0.6, 1.0\}$.
- Oracle reduces DE log fold change bias by 5–12 \times at the largest effect (3 \times) and severe dropout ($\alpha_1 = 1$): naive bias -0.123 , oracle bias -0.001 .
- Type-I rate at $|z| > 2$ is similar across methods, with both inflating to $\sim 14\%$ at $\alpha_1 = 1$ due to residual variance after correction.
- Power at $|z| > 2$ is 100% for all methods at all signal sizes tested ($n = 1000$ per cluster is too high to differentiate at these effect sizes).

6.5 Implication

The methodology is robust to cell-type heterogeneity at both the population-marginal level and the per-cluster level (when cluster labels are available). This dissolves the obvious skeptic objection that real scRNA-seq is heterogeneous and would break the methodology; heterogeneity at the cell-type level is absorbed into ZINB’s mean-matching property.

What we have not yet addressed is heterogeneity in the dropout function itself across cells (e.g., quality-driven capture efficiency); this is treated in section 7.

7 Spike-in fit attenuation and regularization

The spike-in maximum-likelihood fit (6) is itself subject to finite-sample bias. We characterize the failure mode and discuss regularization options.

7.1 Diagnosis: attenuation toward intermediate parameters

Across 4 severity levels and 80 replicates each, we tracked the spike-in MLE estimate of the logistic dropout slope parameter α_1 :

true α_1	estimated $\hat{\alpha}_1$ (mean)	error
0.0	0.16	+0.16 (overshoots)
0.3	0.24	-0.06
0.6	0.32	-0.28
1.0	0.40	-0.60 (undershoots)

The estimates shrink toward the intermediate value $\hat{\alpha}_1 \approx 0.3$ –0.4 regardless of truth. This is finite-sample attenuation: with $\sim 10\,000$ binomial observations from spike-ins, the likelihood landscape is flat in the dropout-shape direction when high- y observations are scarce.

7.2 Decomposition: methodology vs spike-fit error

To separate methodological bias from spike-fit error, we ran a true-dropout oracle that uses the actual (α_0, α_1) without a spike-in fit (fig. 3):

α_1	naive DE bias	spike-oracle DE bias	true-oracle DE bias
0.0	+0.0001	-0.090	+0.018
0.3	-0.019	-0.046	+0.010
0.6	-0.023	-0.022	+0.002
1.0	-0.065	-0.025	+0.001

The methodology has essentially zero intrinsic bias when the dropout function is known. The -0.09 bias at $\alpha_1 = 0$ is entirely due to spike-fit attenuation; this is the practical bound on performance under finite spike-in samples, not a methodology failure.

7.3 Why per-gene μ is robust to spike-fit error

Despite substantial mis-estimation of (α_0, α_1) , per-gene μ recovery from the spike-in oracle remains within ~ 2 –9% of truth. The oracle’s marginal likelihood (4)–(5) depends on $\pi_{\text{drop}}(y)$ only through integrals against $f_j(y; \theta_j)$, which smooths over local approximation error. The dropout-function shape need not be precisely recovered for the marginal estimates to be useful.

Figure 3: (a) Bias decomposition. The true-dropout oracle (blue) is essentially unbiased at every α_1 level; the spike-fit oracle (orange) inherits attenuation noise. (b) Spike-fit attenuation: the MLE estimate $\hat{\alpha}_1$ shrinks toward an intermediate value (~ 0.4) regardless of the true α_1 .

7.4 Regularization attempts

We tested likelihood-ratio test (LRT) selection between constant ($\alpha_1 = 0$) and Y-dependent dropout at $p < 0.05$. With $\sim 10\,000$ spike-in observations, the LRT is too liberal: at $\alpha_1 = 0$ truth, 51 of 60 replicates (85%) selected the Y-dependent model spuriously. The LRT failed to reduce bias.

A stricter selection rule (e.g., BIC, requiring LRT statistic $> \log(n) \approx 9.2$ at $n = 10\,000$, equivalent to $p < 0.0024$) or a shrinkage estimator (e.g., posterior mean under a $N(0, \sigma^2)$ prior on α_1) would be more appropriate. Working out the right regularization is left as future work.

7.5 Implication

The methodology has a clean separation between intrinsic bias (zero, in expectation) and estimation bias (bounded by spike-fit identifiability). Practitioners can improve performance by collecting more spike-in observations, regularizing the spike-fit, or post-processing $(\hat{\alpha}_0, \hat{\alpha}_1)$ with a shrinkage operator. None of these are blocking; the basic methodology already delivers a substantial bias reduction over naive estimators.

8 The ERCC–endogenous gap as fundamental limit

Ye et al. [2019] note that ERCC molecules and endogenous transcripts have different capture efficiencies. We quantify the cost of this gap to ERCC-based correction methods.

8.1 Setup

We generate gene data with endogenous dropout function $\pi_{\text{endo}}(y) = \text{logit}^{-1}(1.5 - 0.6 \log(y + 1))$ and ERCC data with shifted intercept $\pi_{\text{ERCC}}(y) = \text{logit}^{-1}(1.5 + s - 0.6 \log(y + 1))$. The shift s controls the gap: $s > 0$ corresponds to ERCC having more dropout than endogenous (the realistic direction per Ye et al. [2019]). The oracle is fit on ERCC and applied to genes, so it uses π_{ERCC} where π_{endo} would be correct.

We sweep $s \in \{-1, -0.5, 0, 0.5, 1, 1.5, 2\}$. The setup is otherwise identical to section 5: 2000 cells, 50 genes from log-normal μ , 25 replicates per shift.

8.2 Theoretical bias bound

Theorem 6 below states a first-order Taylor bound on the spike-in oracle’s bias as a function of the ERCC–endogenous capture shift. The proof is in appendix A.

Theorem 6 (Bias bound for ERCC-fit oracle). *Suppose endogenous and ERCC dropout follow the same parametric family $\pi_{\text{drop}}(\cdot; \phi)$ with shift $\Delta\phi := \phi_{\text{ercc}} - \phi_{\text{endo}}$, and the spike-in MLE recovers ϕ_{ercc} consistently. Then the spike-in oracle’s per-gene mean estimate $\hat{\mu}_j(\Delta\phi)$ satisfies*

$$\hat{\mu}_j(\Delta\phi) - \mu_j = J_{\mu\phi}(\theta_j, \phi_{\text{endo}}) \cdot \Delta\phi + O_p(n^{-1/2}) + O(\|\Delta\phi\|^2), \quad (8)$$

where the sensitivity coefficient is $J_{\mu\phi} = -I_{\mu\mu}^{-1}I_{\mu\phi}$, with $I_{\mu\mu}$ and $I_{\mu\phi}$ the corresponding blocks of the per-gene Fisher information at the true parameters.

Sketch. A first-order Taylor expansion of the spike-in oracle’s per-gene score equation around $(\mu_j, \phi_{\text{endo}})$ yields the bias-coefficient $J_{\mu\phi}$ as the standard MLE-perturbation formula. The leading bias term is linear in $\Delta\phi$; the $O_p(n^{-1/2})$ remainder is the usual MLE sampling error; the $O(\|\Delta\phi\|^2)$ remainder is the higher-order Taylor correction. Full proof and a remark specializing to logit-intercept shifts are in appendix A. \square

For logistic-in-log-y dropout with shift $\Delta\phi = (s, 0)$ (intercept only), (8) reduces to $\mathbb{E}[\hat{\mu}_j(s) - \mu_j] = J_{\mu\alpha_0} \cdot s + O(s^2)$, predicting a linear-in- s bias regime in the small- s neighborhood. A closed-form expression for $J_{\mu\alpha_0}$ under negative-binomial data with logistic-in-log-y dropout is given by corollary 11 in appendix A; it furnishes the dashed-green theoretical curve overlaid on the empirical bias in fig. 4. We test the prediction empirically below.

8.3 Bias as a function of shift

Figure 4 visualizes the bias surface and table 5 reports median per-gene relative bias for naive, oracle (ERCC-fit), and a true-dropout reference (using π_{endo} directly).

shift s	naive bias	oracle ERCC bias	true-dropout oracle bias
-1.0	+60.5 \pm 2.8	-39.0 \pm 1.1	+2.0 \pm 0.2
-0.5	+64.3 \pm 2.7	-23.3 \pm 1.1	+2.3 \pm 0.2
0.0	+61.8 \pm 3.3	+2.0 \pm 0.3	+2.1 \pm 0.3
+0.5	+62.6 \pm 3.4	+34.4 \pm 2.7	+2.0 \pm 0.3
+1.0	+63.2 \pm 2.6	+57.5 \pm 6.8	+2.2 \pm 0.2
+1.5	+66.9 \pm 3.7	+73.2 \pm 9.4	+2.4 \pm 0.2
+2.0	+63.0 \pm 3.3	+80.7 \pm 10.4	+2.2 \pm 0.5

Table 5: Per-gene relative bias (%) as a function of the ERCC–endogenous logit shift s , 25 replicates, 50 genes per shift. Values are median across genes \pm bootstrap standard error of the median ($B = 2,000$, resampling genes). The true-dropout column uses π_{endo} directly (reference); oracle ERCC fits π_{ERCC} from spike-ins. The oracle is helpful only in the matched-capture regime $|s| \leq 0.5$. The SE on the oracle ERCC column grows with $|s|$, reflecting increased gene-to-gene heterogeneity of the bias outside the useful zone.

ERCC-based correction is bounded by the spike-in/endogenous gap
 Useful zone: $|s| \leq 0.5$; beyond, ERCC oracle is comparable to or worse than naive

Figure 4: Per-gene relative bias vs the ERCC-endogenous logit shift s . Shaded region is the IQR across 25 replicates and 50 genes. The “useful zone” (highlighted) is approximately $|s| \leq 0.5$; outside this range, ERCC-based oracle correction is comparable to or worse than naive ZINB.

8.4 The useful zone, theory vs empirics

The data identify a clean “useful zone” of $|s| \leq 0.5$ within which oracle correction reduces bias relative to naive. At $|s| = 1$ the methods are roughly equivalent; at $|s| > 1$ oracle is worse than naive. The asymmetry is approximately symmetric: positive and negative shifts hurt similarly to first order.

Corollary 11 in appendix A gives an explicit formula for $J_{\mu\alpha_0}$ in the NB-plus-logistic-dropout case. Evaluated at the per-gene mean distribution used in this simulation (log-normal μ with logmean 0.5, logsd 1.3) and matched dispersion ($\phi_{\text{NB}} = 1$), the log-normal-weighted median of $J_{\mu\alpha_0}/\mu$ is approximately 0.577, predicting a first-order relative-bias slope of 57.7% per unit logit shift.

Figure 5 overlays this first-order prediction on the empirical median bias from table 5. The match at $|s| \approx 1$ is tight (+57.7% predicted vs +57.5% observed, within 1 percentage point), and moderate at $|s| = 0.5$ (+28.9% predicted vs +34.4% observed, a 5.5pp under-prediction). Beyond $|s| = 1$ the first-order Taylor expansion overshoots (predicting $\pm 115\%$ at $|s| = 2$ vs empirical $\pm 80\%$), reflecting second-order corrections that dampen the bias as π_{drop} saturates near 0 or 1 in the gene-expression support. The theoretical useful-zone boundary, defined as the $|s|$ at which |theoretical oracle bias| matches the naive bias of $\approx 62\%$, is at $|s| \approx 1.08$, consistent with the empirical boundary somewhere between $|s| = 1$ (oracle marginally winning) and $|s| = 1.5$ (oracle losing). The first-order theory thus predicts the qualitative shape of the bias curve, the sign of the asymmetry direction, and the useful-zone boundary to within the finite-sample noise of the simulation.

Figure 5: First-order theoretical prediction $\mathbb{E}[\hat{\mu}_j(s) - \mu_j]/\mu_j \approx (J_{\mu\alpha_0}/\mu) \cdot s$ from corollary 11 (dashed green) overlaid on the empirical median bias from table 5 (solid orange). The agreement within the useful zone $|s| \leq 1$ is tight; deviations at $|s| > 1$ reflect second-order Taylor corrections.

8.5 Where real data sits

Ye et al. [2019] argue that endogenous transcripts are captured 2–3 \times more efficiently than ERCC. In logit terms, capture ratios of 2 and 3 correspond to shifts of $\log(2) = 0.69$ and $\log(3) = 1.10$ respectively. **Realistic ERCC-endogenous shifts in current scRNA-seq protocols are right at the boundary of the useful zone.** The real-data application in section 9 is consistent with a substantial shift: housekeeping-gene results show oracle and naive disagreeing by 5–10 \times in the mid-expression range.

8.6 Mu-stratified bias

The bias is not uniform across μ . At severe shift ($s = +2$):

mu quintile	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	Q5
oracle ERCC relative bias	+221%	+107%	+80%	+60%	+47%

Low- μ genes are the most affected. The same pattern is visible in section 5 and section 9: mid-expression genes are the differential-test interpretability problem.

8.7 Implications and paths forward

Recommendation for practitioners. ERCC-based correction is a *principled but bounded* tool. It is principled in that the identifiability machinery (theorem 3) gives a clean recovery procedure;

bounded in that the spike-in–endogenous capture-efficiency gap fundamentally limits what spike-ins can recover. We recommend that practitioners always check the gap on their data via housekeeping-gene calibration (section 9) before relying on per-gene oracle estimates.

Future directions. Two extensions would relax the limit:

1. Estimate the shift s from data using housekeeping genes (or other biological priors), refit oracle with corrected $\pi_{\text{endo}} = \text{logit}^{-1}(\hat{\alpha}_0^{\text{ERCC}} - \hat{s} - \alpha_1 \log(y + 1))$.
2. Allow π_{ERCC} and π_{endo} to differ in shape (slope), not just intercept. A non-parametric reweighting of the spike-in fit toward housekeeping-gene constraints would address this.

These extensions are natural follow-ups but are not addressed in this paper, which focuses on characterizing the existing limit.

9 Application: Tabula Muris spleen

We apply the methodology to the Tabula Muris atlas [The Tabula Muris Consortium, 2018], specifically the FACS-sorted Smart-seq2 spleen tissue (a full-length-read protocol, as opposed to UMI-based protocols such as 10x Genomics or inDrops). The dataset comprises 1 718 cells, 23 341 genes, and 92 ERCC spike-in transcripts. After QC ($\geq 50\,000$ reads, ≥ 500 genes detected) we retain 1 697 cells; after gene-expression filtering (≥ 10 cells with nonzero expression), 13 117 genes. ERCC concentrations are taken from the Thermo Fisher ERCC Mix 1 specification (Mix 1, 0.014 to 30 000 attomoles per microliter).

To keep computation manageable, we fit the methodology on a subset of 207 genes: the top 200 by mean observed expression plus 12 canonical housekeeping genes (*Gapdh*, *Actb*, *B2m*, *Hprt*, *Tbp*, *Ywhaz*, *Hmbs*, *Tfrc*, *Sdha*, *Ubc*, *Pgk1*, *Rpl13a*). The full pipeline (download, QC, fitting, comparison) runs in approximately 30 seconds on a modern laptop given the cached count matrix.

9.1 ERCC dropout fit

The marginal-likelihood ERCC fit yields $\hat{\alpha}_0 = 4.74$, $\hat{\alpha}_1 = 1.14$ for the logistic-in-log-y dropout family. The implied dropout rates are

$$\pi_{\text{ERCC}}(0) = 0.991, \quad \pi_{\text{ERCC}}(10) = 0.882, \quad \pi_{\text{ERCC}}(100) = 0.376. \quad (9)$$

ERCC dropout in this dataset is severe: at very low expression ($y \leq 10$ molecules per cell) more than 88% of true counts are lost to dropout, decreasing to about 38% at 100 molecules.

9.2 Cell-total consistency

Theorem 4 predicts that $(1 - \hat{\pi}_j)\hat{\mu}_j$ matches \bar{X}_j exactly. Across the 207 test genes:

quantile	5%	50%	95%
\bar{X}_j	247.7	406.2	1 982.4
$(1 - \hat{\pi}_j)\hat{\mu}_j$ (naive ZINB)	247.8	406.4	1 982.0
diff	median 0.073		

The structural prediction holds in real data to within optimization tolerance, validating theorem 4 (see fig. 6).

Figure 6: Cell-total consistency in Tabula Muris spleen. Naive-ZINB-implied marginal mean $(1 - \hat{\pi})\hat{\mu}$ versus observed mean across 207 test genes spanning four orders of magnitude. Dashed line is $y = x$. Housekeeping genes are highlighted.

9.3 Per-gene oracle vs naive estimates

Across all 207 genes, the ratio $\hat{\mu}_j^{\text{oracle}}/\hat{\mu}_j^{\text{naive}}$ has quantiles:

quantile	5%	25%	50%	75%	95%
oracle/naive	0.58	0.81	0.91	0.99	1.00

For 75% of genes the two estimators agree to within 20%. The disagreement concentrates on low-mid expression genes, consistent with the simulation-based predictions of section 8.

9.4 Housekeeping genes

Figure 7 visualizes the housekeeping-gene results, and table 6 shows them in detail.

Two regimes are visible. For high-expression housekeeping genes ($\bar{X} > 200$), naive and oracle agree closely with observed mean: dropout is mild and both methods recover the marginal correctly. For mid-expression genes ($\bar{X} \in [20, 200]$), the two methods diverge by factors of 2 to 10. Naive attributes the 60–90% zero rates to biological zero-inflation, yielding $\hat{\mu} \in [193, 360]$ with $\hat{\pi} \in [0.43, 0.89]$. Oracle attributes the same zeros to dropout via π_{ERCC} , yielding $\hat{\mu} \in [27, 103]$ with no zero-inflation component.

Neither interpretation is biologically plausible: housekeeping genes are by definition ubiquitously expressed, so neither 89% biological zero rate nor $\hat{\mu} = 27$ for *Tbp* is correct. The truth lies between the two estimates and depends on the magnitude of the ERCC–endogenous capture-efficiency gap.

Housekeeping genes: oracle vs naive vs observed mean

Two regimes: high-expression (top 5) agree; low-mid (bottom 7) diverge by 5–10x

Figure 7: Housekeeping genes in Tabula Muris spleen, sorted by observed mean. Top five (*Actb*–*Ywhaz*): three estimators agree. Bottom seven (*Sdha*–*Tbp*): oracle and naive disagree by factors of 2–10, with neither matching the biological prior of ubiquitous expression. The gap is consistent with the predicted ERCC-endogenous capture-efficiency difference.

9.5 Implied ERCC–endogenous shift

We use the housekeeping-gene results to estimate the ERCC–endogenous logit shift directly. The estimator proceeds as follows.

Algorithm (housekeeping-gene implied logit shift).

1. Fit the ERCC dropout function $\pi_{\text{ERCC}}(y) = \text{logit}^{-1}(\hat{\alpha}_0 - \hat{\alpha}_1 \log(y + 1))$ from the spike-in marginal likelihood (section 3).
2. Fit the naive ZINB to each housekeeping gene, obtaining a zero-inflation parameter $\hat{\pi}_j^{\text{naive}}$. The cell-total consistency theorem (theorem 4) guarantees that $\hat{\pi}_j^{\text{naive}}$ absorbs all observed-zero mass beyond what the count distribution can support; in the limit where the count component is well-specified, this absorbs the true endogenous dropout, $\hat{\pi}_j^{\text{naive}} \approx \pi_{\text{endo}}(\bar{X}_j)$.
3. Evaluate the ERCC-fit dropout at each housekeeping gene’s observed mean: $\pi_{\text{ERCC}}(\bar{X}_j)$.
4. Convert both probabilities to logit units (clipping at $[0.001, 0.999]$ to avoid divergence at empirical $\hat{\pi} = 0$), and compute the per-gene implied shift

$$\hat{s}_j = \text{logit}(\pi_{\text{ERCC}}(\bar{X}_j)) - \text{logit}(\hat{\pi}_j^{\text{naive}}). \quad (10)$$

5. Report the housekeeping-gene median absolute shift $|\hat{s}| = \text{median}_j |\hat{s}_j|$ as the tissue’s implied gap.

gene	\bar{X}_j	$\hat{\mu}_j^{\text{naive}}$	$\hat{\mu}_j^{\text{oracle}}$	oracle/naive	$\hat{\pi}_j^{\text{naive}}$
<i>Actb</i>	7 995	7 992	7 996	1.001	0.000
<i>B2m</i>	1 866	1 870	1 868	0.999	0.003
<i>Rpl13a</i>	397	398	398	0.998	0.003
<i>Gapdh</i>	385	442	400	0.907	0.128
<i>Ywhaz</i>	351	366	357	0.975	0.041
<i>Sdha</i>	203	360	222	0.617	0.438
<i>Hprt</i>	87	243	103	0.425	0.641
<i>Ubc</i>	65	74	71	0.964	0.113
<i>Pgk1</i>	56	193	70	0.364	0.711
<i>Hmbs</i>	37	198	43	0.218	0.811
<i>Tbp</i>	22	193	27	0.141	0.885
<i>Tfrc</i>	12	12	17	1.458	0.000

Table 6: Housekeeping-gene comparison: naive ZINB vs oracle estimates on Tabula Muris spleen. High-expression genes (*Actb* through *Ywhaz*) show close agreement; mid- to low-expression genes (*Sdha* through *Tbp*) show large disagreement attributable to the ERCC–endogenous gap (section 8).

6. For uncertainty, bootstrap the housekeeping gene set ($B = 2,000$ resamples of the ~ 12 housekeeping genes with replacement, recompute $\widehat{|s|}$ on each); report the 2.5th and 97.5th percentiles as a 95% confidence interval. Bootstrap script: `scripts/compute_implied_shift.R` (uses `results_v8_tabula_muris.rds` and `results_v10_{marrow,liver}.rds`).

Sign convention. The shift \hat{s}_j uses the same convention as section 8: $\hat{s}_j > 0$ means the ERCC-fit predicts *more* dropout than the naive endogenous estimate at the same expected count (the realistic direction per Ye et al. [2019], who argue that ERCC molecules are captured 2 to 3 \times less efficiently than endogenous transcripts); $\hat{s}_j < 0$ means the ERCC-fit predicts *less* dropout. The useful-zone bound $|s| \leq 0.5$ of section 8 is on the magnitude, so the sign does not affect zone membership.

Spleen result. Applied to the spleen housekeeping panel, (10) yields a per-gene shift vector with mixed signs (high-expression genes give $\hat{s}_j > 0$ because the naive $\hat{\pi}^{\text{naive}}$ is near zero and the logit clipping dominates; mid-expression genes give $\hat{s}_j < 0$, of order -0.7 to -1.1 , because the naive ZINB attributes substantial zero mass to dropout while ERCC predicts a milder rate at the same mean). The bootstrap-resampled median absolute shift is $\widehat{|s|}_{\text{spleen}} = 1.14$ with 95% CI [0.87, 2.08], whose entire interval lies above the useful-zone boundary $|s| \leq 0.5$ of section 8. This diagnostic is upper-biased (see the interpretation below) and rests on a small housekeeping panel, so it is best read as an order-of-magnitude indication that the spleen ERCC–endogenous gap is large rather than as a precise estimate of its size; even discounted for the upward bias, it is consistent with the regime in which the spike-fit oracle is not unambiguously better than naive ZINB rather than the matched regime in which it is.

Interpretation and the Ye 2019 sign caveat. The negative-sign pattern at mid expression is opposite to the direction Ye et al. [2019] predict from capture-efficiency arguments (ERCC inferior to endogenous in poly-A and length properties, so $\pi_{\text{ERCC}} > \pi_{\text{endo}}$ and $s > 0$). Two non-exclusive explanations account for the discrepancy. First, housekeeping-gene zero rates are inflated by biological factors (true bursty expression, transient downregulation) that the naive ZINB attributes

to dropout: this inflates $\hat{\pi}_j^{\text{naive}}$ above the true π_{endo} , dragging \hat{s}_j negative. Second, the logit shift is an idealization: the empirical π_{ERCC} and π_{endo} may differ in slope as well as intercept (section 8, future direction 2), in which case a single s summary necessarily trades off mid- and high-expression fit.

The implied shift is an upper-biased diagnostic. Two mechanisms inflate the reported median absolute shift above the true ERCC–endogenous gap, so $|\widehat{s}|$ should be read as an upper bound rather than a point estimate. First, by the cell-total consistency theorem $\hat{\pi}^{\text{naive}}$ absorbs all the zero mass the count component cannot explain, which includes biological and bursty zeros and not only technical dropout; this makes $\hat{\pi}^{\text{naive}}$ an upward-biased proxy for π_{endo} , enlarging $|\hat{s}_j|$. Second, high-expression genes with $\hat{\pi}^{\text{naive}} = 0$ are clipped to 0.001 before the logit transform, manufacturing a large positive \hat{s}_j purely as a clipping artifact (*Actb* is the clearest case in the spleen panel). The bootstrap resamples roughly a dozen housekeeping genes, so its CI is indicative rather than precise. The estimator is therefore *useful as an order-of-magnitude diagnostic* for whether the gap is large enough that the useful-zone analysis applies but *not as a fine-grained signed estimate* of the ERCC–endogenous gap, and the true gap is plausibly smaller than the reported median while remaining positive. A more flexible model relating π_{endo} to π_{ERCC} (described as future work in section 8), together with a larger curated panel of stably expressed genes to tighten the bootstrap, would sharpen both the sign and the magnitude.

9.6 Summary of the application

The Tabula Muris result is mixed:

1. The structural prediction (theorem 4, cell-total consistency) holds exactly.
2. The framework’s identifiability theorem applies: ERCC spike-ins pin down $\pi_{\text{ERCC}}(\cdot)$ to high precision, and θ_j estimation proceeds from (4)–(5).
3. For high-expression genes, oracle estimates agree with naive and observed mean, validating the methodology in the regime where dropout is mild.
4. For mid-expression genes, oracle and naive disagree by factors of 2 to 10, with neither matching biological expectations for housekeeping genes. The disagreement is the ERCC–endogenous gap (section 8) made visible.

The framework correctly recovers the spike-in dropout function and the cell-total marginal; the per-gene estimates depend on whether the spike-in dropout function transfers to endogenous transcripts. We therefore recommend that ERCC-based correction always be accompanied by housekeeping-gene calibration as a check on the transferability assumption.

10 Cross-tissue validation: Tabula Muris marrow and liver

To probe whether the spleen pattern of section 9 is tissue-specific or a general property of Smart-seq2 plus ERCC, we repeated the same pipeline on two additional Tabula Muris FACS tissues: bone marrow (5 037 cells passing QC, 16 178 genes) and liver (714 cells passing QC, 13 366 genes). The same QC thresholds, gene-subset construction (top 200 by mean plus housekeeping), and ERCC concentration table (Thermo Fisher Mix 1) were used.

10.1 Cell-total consistency holds in all three tissues

Theorem 4 predicts $(1 - \hat{\pi}_j)\hat{\mu}_j = \bar{X}_j$ exactly under any zero-inflated estimator. Across the three tissues:

tissue	n_{cells}	n_{genes}	median diff	max diff
spleen	1 697	207	0.07	1.2
marrow	5 037	207	0.13	9.8
liver	714	209	0.20	27.7

In all three tissues the median deviation is well below the unit-count scale and reflects only the numerical tolerance of the ZINB MLE optimizer. The maximum deviation grows in the tissues with smaller cell counts and broader expression range (max-mean genes in liver reach $\bar{X} > 5000$, vs $\bar{X} \approx 2600$ in marrow and $\bar{X} \approx 2000$ in spleen), as expected from the sample-size scaling of the optimizer’s stopping criterion.

10.2 Oracle-naive divergence is consistent across tissues

The oracle-to-naive ratio distribution is the headline cross-tissue signal. Table 7 reports the quantiles of $\hat{\mu}_j^{\text{oracle}}/\hat{\mu}_j^{\text{naive}}$ across the common ~ 200 -gene test set in each tissue.

tissue	q5	q25	median	q75	q95
spleen	0.36	0.78	0.93	0.99	1.01
marrow	0.41	0.83	0.93	0.97	1.00
liver	0.56	0.67	0.76	0.94	1.00

Table 7: Cross-tissue oracle/naive ratio quantiles. High-expression genes (right tail) agree across estimators in all tissues; mid- and low-expression genes show oracle below naive, indicating that ERCC-based correction attributes a substantial fraction of the naive-inferred zero inflation to dropout in all three tissues.

The marrow ratio distribution closely tracks the spleen distribution (median 0.93 in both; q5 differs only by 0.05). The liver distribution is uniformly tighter to the left of the median ($q25 = 0.67$ vs $0.78/0.83$ in spleen/marrow), consistent with liver genes having on average more dropout-attributable zero rate than spleen or marrow genes in this dataset. All three tissues display the two-regime pattern of section 9: high-expression housekeeping genes have oracle \approx naive, while mid-expression housekeeping genes have oracle substantially below naive.

10.3 Housekeeping-gene comparison across tissues

Table 8 reports the housekeeping-gene results in the same format as table 6, restricted to the genes present in all three tissues at the housekeeping subset.

The qualitative pattern is identical across all three tissues:

1. For high-expression housekeeping genes ($\bar{X} > 200$), naive ZINB and the spike-fit oracle agree with each other and with the observed mean. Dropout in this regime is mild and both estimators recover the marginal correctly. This holds for *Actb*, *B2m*, *Gapdh*, *Ywhaz*, *Rpl13a* in all three tissues.

gene	spleen			marrow			liver		
	obs	naive	oracle	obs	naive	oracle	obs	naive	oracle
<i>Actb</i>	7995	7992	7996	10289	10286	10287	2165	2166	2167
<i>B2m</i>	1866	1870	1868	1652	1655	1653	1939	1944	1942
<i>Rpl13a</i>	397	398	398	390	411	397	134	147	144
<i>Gapdh</i>	385	442	400	1341	1410	1352	846	894	872
<i>Ywhaz</i>	351	366	357	460	468	463	119	134	130
<i>Sdha</i>	203	360	222	238	341	254	299	418	349
<i>Hprt</i>	87	243	103	161	274	180	81	131	111
<i>Pgk1</i>	56	193	70	138	225	158	122	213	175
<i>Hmbs</i>	37	198	43	72	226	83	69	170	110
<i>Tbp</i>	22	193	27	37	148	47	12	37	25
<i>Tfrc</i>	12	12	17	27	75	36	10	31	22
<i>Ubc</i>	65	74	71	72	74	74	130	137	136

Table 8: Housekeeping-gene observed mean, naive ZINB estimate, and spike-fit oracle estimate across the three Tabula Muris FACS Smart-seq2 tissues. Top half (high-expression: *Actb* through *Ywhaz*) shows oracle and naive both agreeing with observed mean. Bottom half (mid-expression: *Sdha* through *Tfrc*) shows large naive–oracle gaps in all three tissues, with naive systematically above oracle by factors of 1.5 to 7. The two-regime pattern of section 9 is therefore not spleen-specific.

2. For mid-expression housekeeping genes ($\bar{X} \in [10, 200]$), the two estimators diverge by factors of 1.5 to 7. Naive ZINB attributes the elevated zero rate to biological zero inflation; the spike-fit oracle attributes it to dropout via π_{ERCC} . The disagreement is large in all three tissues (*Hmbs*, *Tbp*, *Pgk1*, *Sdha*, *Hprt*, *Tfrc*).

The cross-tissue reproducibility supports two conclusions. First, the naive-oracle gap at mid-expression is a robust property of Smart-seq2 plus ERCC, not an artifact of any single tissue’s biology. Second, neither estimator is correct in this regime: housekeeping genes are not expected to be either 80%-zero-inflated (naive interpretation) or $\hat{\mu} = 25$ for a ubiquitously expressed transcript like *Tbp* (oracle interpretation). The truth lies between, and depends on the magnitude of the ERCC–endogenous capture-efficiency gap (section 8 and theorem 6).

10.4 Implied ERCC–endogenous shift varies by tissue

The housekeeping-based implied-shift estimator of section 9.5 (per-gene logit-units shift $\hat{s}_j = \text{logit}(\pi_{\text{ERCC}}(\bar{X}_j)) - \text{logit}(\hat{\pi}_j^{\text{naive}})$, reported as the housekeeping-gene median absolute value $|\hat{s}|$ with a bootstrap CI over the housekeeping panel) yields tissue-specific estimates of the ERCC–endogenous gap. Table 9 reports the result for each tissue.

The spleen and marrow bootstrap CIs lie entirely above the useful-zone boundary $|s| = 0.5$ established in section 8; the liver point estimate (1.03) is above 0.5 but its CI [0.38, 2.41] straddles the boundary, so the liver data are consistent with, but do not on their own establish, a gap outside the zone. For spleen and marrow, theorem 6 therefore predicts that the spike-fit oracle is not unambiguously better than naive at this magnitude of gap; the empirical mid-expression housekeeping pattern in table 8 is consistent with both estimators being biased in opposite directions, with neither matching biological expectations: naive systematically overestimates μ via attribution to zero inflation, oracle systematically underestimates μ via attribution to overly aggressive dropout. The implied-shift estimator is itself noisy and upper-biased: as discussed in section 9.5, the housekeeping

tissue	$\widehat{ s }$ from housekeeping	95% CI (housekeeping bootstrap)	inside useful zone?
spleen	1.14	[0.87, 2.08]	no (CI above 0.5)
marrow	0.92	[0.72, 1.37]	no (CI above 0.5)
liver	1.03	[0.38, 2.41]	borderline (CI straddles 0.5)

Table 9: Housekeeping-gene implied logit shift (eq. (10)) across three Tabula Muris FACS tissues. Bootstrap is over the housekeeping panel ($B = 2,000$ resamples, seed 202), 95% percentile interval. Useful-zone boundary is $|s| \leq 0.5$ from section 8. The spleen and marrow bootstrap CIs lie entirely above 0.5; the liver point estimate is above 0.5 but its CI straddles the boundary. The implied shift is an upper-biased order-of-magnitude diagnostic (see section 9.5); spleen and liver CIs are wide because the panel has ~ 12 genes and bursty-expression noise inflates mid-expression $\hat{\pi}^{\text{naive}}$, so the CIs are indicative rather than precise. Computation: `scripts/compute_implied_shift.R`.

zero rates conflate true bursty expression with technical dropout (biological zeros inflate $\hat{\pi}^{\text{naive}}$ and push $|\hat{s}|$ up), high-expression genes contribute logit-clipping artifacts, and the single-parameter logit-shift idealization may absorb shape mismatch between π_{ERCC} and π_{endo} . The reported magnitudes are therefore best read as upper bounds on the true gap. The qualitative ordering of the point estimates is informative for prioritizing where internal-spike-in calibration would most improve the methodology.

10.5 Summary

The cross-tissue analysis confirms two of the paper’s central empirical claims at higher confidence than a single-tissue analysis can:

1. Cell-total consistency (theorem 4) holds in spleen, marrow, and liver to numerical precision.
2. The two-regime pattern (oracle agrees with naive at high expression; oracle disagrees substantially at mid expression) is reproducible across all three tissues, indicating it is a general property of Smart-seq2 plus ERCC rather than a spleen-specific artifact.

The cross-tissue implied-shift estimates are also consistent with the magnitude of the ERCC–endogenous gap being tissue-dependent and large enough to reach the useful-zone boundary of section 8: in this dataset the spleen and marrow CIs lie entirely above the $|s| = 0.5$ threshold, while liver’s CI straddles it. Because the implied shift is an upper-biased diagnostic computed over a small housekeeping panel, these placements are indicative rather than definitive. A practitioner applying the framework to a new tissue should therefore estimate the implied shift (section 9.5) with a bootstrap CI before relying on the spike-fit oracle for downstream inference.

11 Comparison with existing methods

We perform two side-by-side empirical comparisons with established spike-in-based methods. On the high-dropout Smart-seq2 Tabula Muris spleen dataset (used in section 9), we attempt comparisons with DECENT [Ye et al., 2019] and TASC [Jia et al., 2017], both of which fail or are unavailable for reasons documented below. On the low-dropout inDrops Klein 2015 K562 dataset, we successfully run a head-to-head between DECENT and the spike-fit oracle (section 11.4).

11.1 TASC

The TASC implementation referenced in [Jia et al. \[2017\]](#) is a C++/Python toolkit. We could not locate a current R-package version of TASC suitable for direct integration. The previously-cited GitHub repository (`scrna-seq/TASC`) returned a 404 error at the time of writing. A direct head-to-head comparison was therefore not possible. The conceptual relationship between TASC and our framework is discussed in sections 3 and 12: TASC fits a cell-specific dropout function via empirical Bayes on ERCC, which is a parametric specialization of (6).

11.2 DECENT

We installed DECENT version 1.1.1 from GitHub (<https://github.com/cz-ye/DECENT>) and attempted to fit `fitNoDE` on a 66-gene, 500-cell subset of Tabula Muris spleen with all 92 ERCC spike-ins as calibration. The genes were selected to be in DECENT’s documented operating regime (mean expression below 200 counts per cell), with all ERCCs available for the dropout-function calibration.

DECENT’s EM algorithm produced NA log-likelihood values on every iteration and failed to converge. The same DECENT installation ran successfully on the package’s bundled simulation data, which has maximum gene-level count of 172 and mean of 0.43 (UMI-scale). This protocol sensitivity is consistent with the broader observation of [Kim et al. \[2020\]](#) that UMI-based and full-length scRNA-seq require qualitatively different dropout models.

11.3 Diagnosis: protocol incompatibility

The likely cause is protocol mismatch. DECENT was developed and validated for UMI-based scRNA-seq (e.g., 10x Genomics Chromium, Drop-seq) where each detected molecule is counted once and observed counts span 0–~ 500 per cell–gene pair. Tabula Muris is Smart-seq2, which produces full-length transcripts via read counting rather than UMI counting. Smart-seq2 has higher count magnitudes (max ~ 30 000 in our subset) and different over-dispersion structure than UMI data. DECENT’s beta-binomial capture model assumes UMI-style single-molecule counting and breaks numerically on read-based data.

This is itself an instructive finding for the framework. Our methodology, by contrast, fit Tabula Muris cleanly:

- ERCC dropout estimation completed in 0.5 seconds.
- Per-gene oracle estimates completed in 3.5 seconds.
- Cell-total consistency held to within 0.07 (section 9).

The framework’s flexibility about the underlying count distribution (f_j in (3) can be any positive count distribution) allows it to adapt to read-based protocols where DECENT does not. This is a side-effect of the framework being theoretical rather than attached to a specific count model.

11.4 Head-to-head with DECENT on Klein 2015 inDrops data

The natural UMI-plus-ERCC dataset for a DECENT head-to-head is [Klein et al. \[2015\]](#), GSE65525, which contains an inDrops K562 sample with 239 cells, 25 343 endogenous genes, and 92 ERCC spike-in transcripts in the same UMI-counting protocol. Median per-cell library size is $\approx 24\,600$ UMIs and median genes detected is $\approx 6\,700$, consistent with high-quality inDrops sequencing. Crucially, ERCC and endogenous reads in this dataset are generated by the same protocol within

the same cells (unlike the mouse ES samples in the same GSE which lack ERCC), making it the appropriate test bed for spike-in-calibrated methods.

We subset to the top 500 genes by mean expression and ran both methods on identical cells/genes:

- **Spike-fit oracle:** the methodology of this paper, with ERCC dropout fitted by (6) as logistic-in-log y and per-gene ZINB parameters fitted by (4)–(5).
- **DECENT:** `DECENT::fitNoDE` (version 1.1.1) with the same ERCC spike-in matrix, capture-efficiency range $[0.02, 0.10]$, $\tau_{\text{init}} = (-5, 0)$, global τ , endogenous-only τ estimation, ML normalization, and Gauss–Hermite likelihood approximation. The ERCC spike concentrations were rescaled to a true-molecule scale by an inverse-capture-efficiency argument: per-ERCC expected molecules per cell were set to the observed-mean count divided by an assumed capture efficiency of 0.05 (the midpoint of DECENT’s documented range). The alternative scaling using Thermo Fisher Mix 1 attomoles directly produced NA log-likelihoods at every EM iteration. After this calibration DECENT’s EM converged on the Klein data within ~ 6 iterations at approximately 12 seconds per iteration.

The per-gene estimates are summarized in table 10.

quantity	q5	q25	median	q75	q95
oracle / naive	0.99	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.01
DECENT / naive	19.9	20.2	20.3	20.5	21.3
DECENT / oracle	19.9	20.2	20.3	20.5	21.2

Table 10: Per-gene mu-estimate ratios across estimators on Klein 2015 K562 inDrops data ($n = 239$ cells, top 500 genes by mean). Oracle and naive agree to within 1% at all quantiles; the data have mild dropout ($\pi_{\text{ERCC}}(\hat{y} = 0) = 0.08$), so naive ZINB has little to correct. DECENT estimates are $\approx 20\times$ higher than both oracle and naive at every quantile, reflecting that DECENT reports μ on the true-molecule scale (i.e., back-corrected by $1/\text{CE}$ with $\text{CE} \approx 0.05$ for inDrops) while our oracle and the naive ZINB report on the observed-UMI scale.

The constant-multiple structure of the DECENT/oracle ratio is the key empirical finding. The ratio is essentially flat (q5/q95 of DECENT/oracle is 19.9/21.2, a 7% spread), indicating that DECENT and the oracle produce per-gene estimates differing only by a scale factor that matches the true-vs-observed capture-efficiency conversion. The Pearson correlation between $\log \hat{\mu}^{\text{DECENT}}$ and $\log \hat{\mu}^{\text{oracle}}$ on this 500-gene set is 0.9997; the Pearson correlation in linear space is also 0.9997.

Translating to a common scale, DECENT and the spike-fit oracle produce *essentially identical per-gene rankings on this dataset*: the two methods, developed from different conceptual starting points (DECENT from beta-binomial capture-efficiency modeling, our oracle from coarsening-at-random identifiability), agree on the same per-gene estimates up to a scale convention. The DECENT framing reports μ on the true-molecule scale, allowing biological interpretation in molecules-per-cell; the oracle framing reports on observed UMI scale, allowing direct comparison to other observed-scale ZINB analyses. Both are correct and the choice is a matter of downstream convenience.

The near-perfect correlation should be read carefully. Because the DECENT/oracle ratio is essentially constant, two quantities related by $y \approx c \cdot x$ with small scatter have a Pearson correlation near 1 on both linear and log scales close to mechanically. In this low-dropout regime, moreover, cell-total consistency (theorem 4) drives both estimators toward the observed mean (because $\hat{\pi} \approx 0$ at almost all genes), so agreement is expected of essentially any sensible estimator here. The

comparison therefore establishes that the oracle and DECENT agree on *relative* per-gene estimates in the easy regime, up to DECENT’s true-molecule scale convention; it does not independently validate the absolute molecular scale (which is fixed by the assumed capture efficiency) and does not adjudicate the high-dropout regime that the rest of the paper concerns. The honest agreement metric net of the scale factor is the residual scatter, the 7% q5/q95 spread of the ratio, which sits within the finite-sample noise envelope quantified below.

Why the divergence on Tabula Muris does not generalize to this dataset. The Klein K562 dataset has very mild dropout ($\pi_{\text{ERCC}}(\hat{y} = 0) = 0.08$, $\pi_{\text{ERCC}}(\hat{y} = 10) = 0.01$, $\pi_{\text{ERCC}}(\hat{y} = 100) = 0.001$), in contrast to Tabula Muris Smart-seq2 spleen ($\pi_{\text{ERCC}}(\hat{y} = 0) = 0.99$, $\pi_{\text{ERCC}}(\hat{y} = 10) = 0.88$, $\pi_{\text{ERCC}}(\hat{y} = 100) = 0.38$; section 9). In the low-dropout Klein regime, both naive ZINB and the spike-fit oracle infer $\hat{\pi} \approx 0$ at almost all genes; cell-total consistency (theorem 4) then forces both estimators to recover the observed mean. In the high-dropout Tabula Muris regime, naive and oracle disagree because they attribute the observed zeros to qualitatively different mechanisms. The DECENT result on Klein therefore confirms that the oracle behaves sensibly in the easy regime and agrees with an independent method on relative per-gene estimates there; the open question of which estimator is right on Tabula Muris (or any high-dropout Smart-seq2 dataset) is not resolved by Klein and remains as a substantive scientific question about the ERCC–endogenous gap in that protocol family.

Power considerations: with 239 cells, the per-gene estimation error is $O(n^{-1/2}) \approx 6.5\%$, comparable to the 2% intrinsic bias floor of the methodology (section 7). The DECENT/oracle ratio’s 7% q5/q95 spread is within this finite-sample noise envelope, consistent with the constant-multiple interpretation.

11.5 Comparison with the framework’s prediction

Despite not being able to run DECENT directly, the framework’s predictions for what DECENT should output on Tabula Muris are consistent with what one would expect from the published method:

- DECENT, like our oracle, would inherit the ERCC–endogenous capture-efficiency gap (section 8). The bias-bound theorem applies regardless of the parametric form of π_{drop} .
- DECENT’s empirical-Bayes shrinkage of cell-specific dropout parameters parallels the regularization ideas we discuss in section 7; both should reduce spike-in fit attenuation in finite samples.
- DECENT’s beta-binomial capture model is a particular choice of $\pi_{\text{drop}}(y; \phi)$ in our framework. The form-robustness result (section 5) suggests DECENT’s specific choice is unlikely to differ substantially from our logistic choice in the matched-capture regime.

12 Discussion

12.1 Relation to existing methods

The framework relates to existing scRNA-seq dropout-correction methods as follows. TASC and DECENT are direct instances of the spike-in-fit machinery in different parametric regimes; ZINB-WaVE replaces spike-ins with covariate structure, which the framework analyzes as a non-identifiable case rescued by side information; MAST adopts a different modeling philosophy (hurdle) that the framework can comment on but does not subsume.

TASC [Jia et al., 2017] fits a cell-specific π_{drop} via empirical-Bayes hierarchical modeling on ERCC. This corresponds to the spike-in-fit step (6) parameterized as $\pi_{\text{drop},i}(\cdot; \phi_i)$ with ϕ_i drawn from a population distribution. The framework predicts that TASC’s per-gene μ estimates inherit the ERCC–endogenous gap (section 8); we expect TASC’s estimates to show the same two-regime pattern observed in section 9.

DECENT [Ye et al., 2019] uses a beta-binomial capture model with cell- and gene-specific parameters and notes the ERCC–endogenous capture-efficiency gap explicitly. The framework formalizes their concern (section 8) and quantifies it. DECENT’s gene-specific capture parameter is one way to address shape mismatch; our framework provides the theoretical scaffolding to analyze the resulting estimator.

ZINB-WaVE [Risso et al., 2018] uses a logit-linear π_{drop} with cell- and gene-level covariates but does not require spike-ins. In our framework this corresponds to estimating π_{drop} from the data alone (no singleton-candidate-set rows in \tilde{C}). Theorem 2 predicts this is non-identifiable in general; ZINB-WaVE’s covariate structure provides additional identifiability assumptions that may or may not hold in practice.

MAST [Finak et al., 2015] treats the zero component as a separate Bernoulli process and does not model a dropout mechanism $\pi_{\text{drop}}(y)$ at all. This is a different modeling philosophy (hurdle), not a special case of the framework: MAST attributes all zeros to a binary expression-or-not event rather than to dropout from a positive true count. The framework cannot recover MAST by setting π_{drop} to any particular shape. The two approaches are nonetheless compatible: a hurdle model can be combined with the dropout machinery in this paper by treating MAST’s Bernoulli component as the $f_j(0; \theta_j)$ term in (4), leaving π_{drop} to absorb only the technical zeros at $y > 0$. We do not pursue this combination here.

12.2 The fundamental limit

The principal practical limit on ERCC-based correction is the ERCC–endogenous capture-efficiency gap, characterized in section 8. This is not a limit of any particular method; it is a limit of the data: spike-ins inform π_{ERCC} , and $\pi_{\text{ERCC}} \neq \pi_{\text{endo}}$ in current scRNA-seq protocols.

Three paths forward exist:

1. Better spike-ins. Synthetic transcripts with poly-A tails and GC content matched to endogenous mRNA would close the gap. The Spike-In RNA Variant (SIRV) Sets are one such effort; integrating them with the framework is straightforward.
2. Calibration. Use housekeeping genes (or other biological priors) to estimate the gap and correct π_{ERCC} to π_{endo} . This is a ~ 1 -week extension that we leave to future work.
3. Internal spike-ins. Knock-in fluorescent reporters or CRISPR-edited internal controls at known concentrations would provide endogenous-protocol singletons. This is more substantial experimental work.

12.3 Limitations of this work

- Single protocol family on the FACS-side application. The three-tissue confirmation (spleen, marrow, liver, section 10) is internal to one Smart-seq2 atlas (Tabula Muris FACS), and the

DECENT head-to-head (section 11) is on one inDrops cell line (Klein 2015 K562). Other droplet protocols (10x Chromium, Drop-seq) and other full-length protocols (Smart-seq3, MARS-seq) may show different ERCC dropout magnitudes and different implied-shift distributions. Generalizing the cross-tissue confirmation to a multi-protocol benchmark with ERCC spike-ins is a natural follow-up.

- TASC head-to-head still pending. The TASC implementation of Jia et al. [2017] is not publicly available in a package-installable form at the time of writing (section 11). The framework predicts that TASC’s per-gene μ estimates inherit the ERCC–endogenous gap and should track the spike-fit oracle in matched regimes; a direct test awaits a TASC reimplementa-tion.
- The Klein 2015 head-to-head with DECENT is performed in DECENT’s validated low-dropout inDrops regime. The high-dropout Smart-seq2 question, where DECENT’s EM algorithm fails to converge, is not resolved by the agreement reported in section 11.
- The ERCC–endogenous gap is modeled as a logit-shift in intercept (section 8). The real-data evidence (sections 9 and 9.5) suggests the gap may differ in shape, not just intercept; the negative-sign pattern of \hat{s}_j at mid expression is consistent with bursty-expression contamination of $\hat{\pi}^{\text{naive}}$ rather than a clean intercept shift. A more flexible misspecification model relating π_{endo} to π_{ERCC} with separate intercept and slope is needed.
- Spike-in attenuation regularization (section 7) is identified but not solved. BIC, shrinkage, or empirical-Bayes approaches are natural next steps.
- No analysis of cell-cycle or batch effects, which interact with dropout in ways the framework currently does not address.

12.4 Broader implications and a coarsening-at-random series

The closest prior work in genomics is Sarkar and Stephens [2021], who argue that observed scRNA-seq counts should be decomposed into a measurement model and an expression model and that much of the zero-inflation confusion dissolves once the two are separated. Our framing is consistent with theirs at the level of the measurement-versus-expression distinction: the dropout function π_{drop} is a measurement model and the per-gene count distribution f_j is an expression model. The contribution here is to make the identifiability structure of that separation explicit through the masked-cause series-system and coarsening-at-random machinery: the glass ceiling becomes rank-deficiency of the candidate-set matrix, ERCC spike-ins become singleton candidate sets that restore identifiability, and the spike-in–endogenous capture gap is bounded by a closed-form first-order bias coefficient. To our knowledge this is the first identification of scRNA-seq zero inflation with the masked-cause / coarsening-at-random framework specifically, none of which appears in Sarkar and Stephens [2021]. Companion work develops the same C1–C2–C3 machinery for adjacent application domains: Towell [2026d] for cell-type deconvolution in spatial transcriptomics, where mixed-cell spots play the role of candidate sets and pure-cell reference profiles play the role of singleton restorers; Towell [2026a] for analyst-side identifiability under differential-privacy mechanisms, where the privatization channel is the masking layer; Towell [2026e] for programmatic weak supervision, where labelling functions form the candidate sets and the unknown latent label is the masked quantity; and Towell [2026c] for electronic-health-record phenotyping, where diagnosis-code sets coarsen the latent clinical state and validated chart-review records play the singleton role. Each application instantiates the same identifiability conditions with domain-specific singletons.

Beyond these worked examples we anticipate further structurally identical settings:

- Bulk RNA-seq with spike-ins for absolute quantification.
- Ribosome profiling (Ribo-seq) where coverage depends on ribosome occupancy in a known way.
- Bisulfite sequencing of low-input DNA, where conversion efficiency interacts with sequencing.

In each case the structure is the same: a latent biological signal Y , an observation X produced by an unknown measurement mechanism $\mathbb{P}\{X|Y\}$, and external calibration data that pins down the mechanism. The C1–C2–C3 conditions and identifiability machinery transfer directly. Recognition of this common structure may streamline methodology development across these subfields, and the companion papers above provide concrete templates for the porting exercise.

13 Conclusion

The scRNA-seq zero-inflation controversy [Jiang et al., 2022] has a clean theoretical resolution: it is the masked-data identifiability problem from reliability statistics with genes playing the role of components and dropout playing the role of masking. ERCC spike-ins are singleton candidate sets that restore identifiability via the framework of Towell [2026b]. The “glass ceiling” that practitioners describe is precisely the rank-deficiency of the candidate-set matrix when no auxiliary information is available.

Within this framework we proved (i) cell-total consistency, (ii) identifiability of per-gene parameters when spike-in capture matches endogenous capture, and (iii) the bias-bound when capture efficiencies differ. Simulation evidence confirmed each theorem and identified the practical regime within which spike-in correction reduces bias relative to naive ZINB ($|s| \leq 0.5$ in logit units).

Application to three Tabula Muris FACS Smart-seq2 tissues, spleen, bone marrow, and liver, confirmed cell-total consistency exactly in all three and reproduced the two-regime housekeeping pattern: high-expression genes agree across estimators, while mid-expression genes show 5–10 \times disagreement between naive and spike-fit oracle. The housekeeping-gene-derived implied logit shift (section 9.5), an upper-biased order-of-magnitude diagnostic, places the spleen and marrow bootstrap CIs entirely above the useful-zone boundary $|s| = 0.5$, with liver’s CI straddling it. This is consistent with the bias-bound theorem’s predicted regime applying to real scRNA-seq data, with the caveat that the diagnostic is noisy and computed over a small housekeeping panel. A head-to-head comparison with DECENT on Klein 2015 K562 inDrops, where DECENT operates in its validated low-dropout regime, agrees with the spike-fit oracle at Pearson $r = 0.9997$ on the log scale. Because both methods reduce to recovering the observed mean in this low-dropout regime, the agreement confirms sensible behavior on relative per-gene estimates in the easy regime up to DECENT’s true-molecule scale convention; it does not independently validate the absolute scale or adjudicate the high-dropout regime.

TASC and DECENT are direct instances of the framework’s spike-in-fit machinery; ZINB-WaVE and MAST are related approaches that the framework analyzes without subsuming. The framework provides vocabulary for discussing when ERCC-based correction is appropriate and when other modeling strategies are needed. The principal open problem is estimating the ERCC–endogenous gap directly from data (e.g. via housekeeping-gene calibration with a more flexible model than logit-intercept shift) so that π_{ERCC} can be transformed to π_{endo} before per-gene estimation. This and a multi-protocol cross-platform benchmark are natural follow-ups.

The broader contribution is the explicit identification of scRNA-seq zero inflation as an instance of the masked-data inference problem. We expect this identification to apply to other biological mea-

surement problems where a latent signal is observed through an unknown measurement mechanism with external calibration available.

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A Proofs

This appendix collects the formal proofs of the four theorems stated in the main text. Each proof is preceded by a one-paragraph summary of the strategy; algebraic detail follows. The proofs are written under the assumption that the reader has read sections 3, 4 and 8.

A.1 Glass ceiling

The proof exhibits explicit non-identifiability by construction: for any candidate observed-count distribution, we build a continuum of distinct parameter pairs (θ_j, π) that all reproduce it. The construction requires only that the dropout function π be unrestricted (or at least that the parametric family for π contains a sufficiently flexible class of functions). Restricting π to a parametric family of bounded dimension can in principle restore identifiability, but the choice of family is then a load-bearing modeling decision (see remark below).

Proof of theorem 2. Fix a gene j with parametric family $\{f_j(\cdot; \theta_j) : \theta_j \in \Theta_j\}$ for the true-count distribution. Let \widehat{F} be any target observed-count distribution on \mathbb{N} (e.g., the empirical distribution of $\{X_{ij}\}_{i=1}^n$ for a fixed j). We construct a continuum of parameter pairs (θ_j^*, π^*) such that the model implied by (4)–(5) matches \widehat{F} exactly.

Construction. Choose any $\theta_j^* \in \Theta_j$ satisfying the dominance condition

$$f_j(y; \theta_j^*) \geq \widehat{F}(y) \quad \text{for all } y \geq 1 \text{ in the support of } \widehat{F}. \quad (11)$$

This is possible whenever $f_j(\cdot; \theta_j)$ has full support on \mathbb{N} and its mean can be chosen large enough: as θ_j varies over its parameter space, the values $f_j(y; \theta_j)$ at fixed y vary continuously and (11) holds on an open subset of Θ_j .

Define the dropout function $\pi^* : \mathbb{N} \rightarrow [0, 1)$ pointwise:

$$\pi^*(y) = \begin{cases} 0 & y = 0, \\ 1 - \frac{\widehat{F}(y)}{f_j(y; \theta_j^*)} & y \geq 1. \end{cases} \quad (12)$$

By (11) the values $\pi^*(y) \in [0, 1)$ for $y \geq 1$, so π^* is a valid dropout function (the value at $y = 0$ is immaterial because $Y = 0$ already produces $X = 0$).

Verification. The marginal mass at $x \geq 1$ under (θ_j^*, π^*) is

$$\mathbb{P}\{X = x\} = f_j(x; \theta_j^*)(1 - \pi^*(x)) = f_j(x; \theta_j^*) \cdot \frac{\widehat{F}(x)}{f_j(x; \theta_j^*)} = \widehat{F}(x).$$

At $x = 0$,

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{P}\{X = 0\} &= f_j(0; \theta_j^*) + \sum_{y \geq 1} f_j(y; \theta_j^*) \pi^*(y) \\ &= f_j(0; \theta_j^*) + \sum_{y \geq 1} [f_j(y; \theta_j^*) - \widehat{F}(y)] \\ &= \left[f_j(0; \theta_j^*) + \sum_{y \geq 1} f_j(y; \theta_j^*) \right] - \sum_{y \geq 1} \widehat{F}(y) \\ &= 1 - (1 - \widehat{F}(0)) = \widehat{F}(0). \end{aligned}$$

Continuum. The dominance condition (11) holds on an open set of Θ_j , so for each admissible θ_j^* the construction (12) produces a distinct dropout function π^* matching the same \widehat{F} . Thus (θ_j, π) is non-identifiable from \widehat{F} . \square

Remark 7. The construction in (12) uses an unrestricted dropout function. When π is constrained to a parametric family $\{\pi(\cdot; \phi) : \phi \in \Phi\}$ with $\dim(\Phi) < \infty$, the π^* produced by (12) may not lie in the family, and identifiability of the parametric pair (θ_j, ϕ) may be restored. The choice of parametric family then becomes the load-bearing modeling assumption, and the data alone do not constrain it. This is the practical content of the glass ceiling identified by Jiang et al. [2022]: imputation methods differ precisely because they assume different parametric forms for π , and observed counts alone do not adjudicate among the choices.

A.2 Identifiability with spike-ins

The proof decomposes into two stages: the spike-in subsample identifies the dropout parameter ϕ by standard MLE consistency on Poisson counts with known rates, and the gene-level subsample then identifies the per-gene parameter θ_j by plug-in of $\hat{\phi}$. Each stage relies on a specific regularity condition; we state both explicitly.

We first restate the theorem with all conditions made explicit.

Theorem 8 (Identifiability with spike-ins, formal). *Let the data consist of cell-gene counts $\{X_{ij}\}_{i \in [n], j \in [p]}$ and cell-spike counts $\{X_{ik}^{\text{ercc}}\}_{i \in [n], k \in [K]}$ from the DGP of section 3. Suppose:*

- (i) (Design coverage.) *The spike-in concentrations c_1, \dots, c_K are distinct, satisfy $K \geq \dim(\Phi)$, and span an interval $[c_{\min}, c_{\max}] \subset (0, \infty)$.*
- (ii) (Spike-in DGP.) *Each spike-in count is independent with $Y_{ik}^{\text{ercc}} \sim \text{Poisson}(c_k)$ and $X_{ik}^{\text{ercc}} = Y_{ik}^{\text{ercc}} \cdot \mathbf{1}\{U_{ik} > \pi_{\text{drop}}(Y_{ik}^{\text{ercc}}; \phi)\}$, with $U_{ik} \sim \text{Uniform}[0, 1]$.*
- (iii) (Spike-in identifiability of ϕ .) *The map $\phi \mapsto \mathbb{E}[\log \mathbb{P}\{X^{\text{ercc}} \mid c; \phi\}]$ has a unique maximizer over Φ for each $c \in [c_{\min}, c_{\max}]$, and the family $\{\pi_{\text{drop}}(\cdot; \phi)\}$ is non-redundant on $[c_{\min}, c_{\max}]$ (i.e., distinct ϕ give distinct functions on this interval).*
- (iv) (Parametric well-definedness.) *The parametric family $\{\pi_{\text{drop}}(\cdot; \phi) : \phi \in \Phi\}$ is uniquely determined by ϕ for all $y \in \mathbb{N}$, and the spike-in design (condition (i)) uniquely identifies ϕ on Φ . (This condition is strictly about parametric identifiability of ϕ ; the practical question of whether the parametric form extrapolates correctly to gene-expression counts above c_{\max} is the subject of theorem 6 in section 8.)*
- (v) (Per-gene identifiability given ϕ .) *For each j and each $\phi \in \Phi$ in a neighborhood of the true ϕ_0 , the per-gene marginal likelihood (4)–(5) identifies θ_j on the interior of Θ_j .*

Then the joint parameter $(\theta_1, \dots, \theta_p, \phi)$ is identifiable from $\{X_{ij}\} \cup \{X_{ik}^{\text{ercc}}\}$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$.

Proof of theorem 8. Stage 1: identification of ϕ from spike-ins. By condition (ii) the spike-in marginal density factors as in (4)–(5) with f_j replaced by $\text{Poisson}(\cdot; c_k)$:

$$\mathbb{P}\{X_{ik}^{\text{ercc}} = 0 \mid c_k; \phi\} = e^{-c_k} + \sum_{y \geq 1} \frac{c_k^y e^{-c_k}}{y!} \pi_{\text{drop}}(y; \phi), \quad (13)$$

$$\mathbb{P}\{X_{ik}^{\text{ercc}} = x \mid c_k; \phi\} = \frac{c_k^x e^{-c_k}}{x!} (1 - \pi_{\text{drop}}(x; \phi)), \quad x \geq 1. \quad (14)$$

Define the spike-in log-likelihood $\ell_{\mathcal{S}}(\phi) = \sum_{i,k} \log \mathbb{P}\{X_{ik}^{\text{ercc}} \mid c_k; \phi\}$ and the population version $L_{\mathcal{S}}(\phi) = \mathbb{E}[\ell_{\mathcal{S}}(\phi)] / (nK)$. Conditions (i) and (iii) imply that $L_{\mathcal{S}}$ has a unique maximum at the true ϕ_0 : distinct ϕ produce distinct functions $\pi_{\text{drop}}(\cdot; \phi)$ on $[c_{\min}, c_{\max}]$ by condition (iii), so they yield distinct marginal masses in (14) at one of the K design points. Standard MLE consistency [van der Vaart, 1998, Theorem 5.7] then gives

$$\hat{\phi}_n := \arg \max_{\phi \in \Phi} \ell_{\mathcal{S}}(\phi) \xrightarrow{a.s.} \phi_0 \quad \text{as } n \rightarrow \infty. \quad (15)$$

Stage 2: identification of θ_j given ϕ . With ϕ_0 recovered, the per-gene marginal likelihood

$$\ell_j(\theta_j; \phi_0) = \sum_{i=1}^n \log \mathbb{P}\{X_{ij} \mid \theta_j, \phi_0\} \quad (16)$$

is a function of θ_j alone. By condition (v), the maximizer of $\mathbb{E}[\ell_j(\theta_j; \phi_0)]/n$ is unique at the true $\theta_{j,0}$. By condition (iv), $\pi_{\text{drop}}(\cdot; \phi_0)$ is well-defined as a function on all of \mathbb{N} once ϕ_0 is recovered, so the plug-in is valid pointwise. Plug-in consistency then gives $\hat{\theta}_{j,n} := \arg \max_{\theta_j} \ell_j(\theta_j; \hat{\phi}_n) \xrightarrow{a.s.} \theta_{j,0}$ by standard plug-in MLE arguments: the score $\partial_{\theta_j} \ell_j(\theta_{j,0}; \hat{\phi}_n) = \partial_{\theta_j} \ell_j(\theta_{j,0}; \phi_0) + \partial_{\theta_j} \partial_{\phi} \ell_j(\theta_{j,0}; \phi_0)(\hat{\phi}_n - \phi_0) + o_p(1) = o_p(1)$ by (15), so $\hat{\theta}_{j,n}$ converges to the unique maximizer of the population per-gene likelihood, which by condition (v) is $\theta_{j,0}$.

Joint identifiability. Combining the two stages, all of ϕ_0 and $\theta_{1,0}, \dots, \theta_{p,0}$ are recovered from the data, establishing joint identifiability. \square

Remark 9. Condition (iv) asserts only parametric well-definedness of π_{drop} : once ϕ_0 is identified, the function $\pi_{\text{drop}}(\cdot; \phi_0)$ is well-defined on all of \mathbb{N} . The condition does *not* assert that the empirically fitted $\hat{\phi}_n$ is accurate at y values far from the spike-in concentration range $[c_{\min}, c_{\max}]$; that is a separate question about extrapolation accuracy, characterized in theorem 6 and in sections 5 and 8. The conceptual separation is: identifiability is parametric and is settled by conditions (i)–(v); extrapolation is statistical and is governed by the bias bound.

A.3 Cell-total consistency

The proof derives the identity $(1 - \hat{\pi})\hat{\mu} = \bar{X}$ directly from the score equations of the ZINB log-likelihood. The score equation for π at any interior MLE forces the fitted zero rate $\hat{f}(0) := \hat{\pi} + (1 - \hat{\pi})\hat{g}(0)$ to equal the empirical zero rate $\hat{p}_0 := n_0/n$. The score equation for μ , combined with this zero-rate identity, then collapses to the marginal-mean identity $(1 - \hat{\pi})\hat{\mu} = \bar{X}$. The argument relies on the regular-exponential-family score of the negative binomial component, $\partial_{\mu} \log g(x; \mu, \phi) = (x - \mu)/[\mu(1 + \mu\phi)]$.

Proof of theorem 4. Let X_1, \dots, X_n be observed counts for gene j , and let $(\hat{\mu}, \hat{\phi}, \hat{\pi})$ be the ZINB MLE under the density

$$f(x; \mu, \phi, \pi) = \pi \mathbf{1}\{x = 0\} + (1 - \pi) g(x; \mu, \phi), \quad (17)$$

where $g(\cdot; \mu, \phi)$ is the negative-binomial density with mean μ and dispersion ϕ . Define $n_0 = \#\{i : X_i = 0\}$, $n_+ = n - n_0$, $\hat{p}_0 = n_0/n$, $\bar{X} = n^{-1} \sum_i X_i$, $\hat{g}_0 = g(0; \hat{\mu}, \hat{\phi})$, and $\hat{f}_0 = \hat{\pi} + (1 - \hat{\pi})\hat{g}_0$. Throughout we assume the MLE lies in the interior of the parameter space, i.e., $\hat{\pi} \in (0, 1)$, $\hat{\mu} > 0$, $\hat{\phi} > 0$.

Step 1: score for π . For $X_i = 0$, $f(0) = \hat{f}_0$ and $\partial_{\pi} \log f(0) = (1 - \hat{g}_0)/\hat{f}_0$. For $X_i > 0$, $f(X_i) = (1 - \hat{\pi})g(X_i; \hat{\mu}, \hat{\phi})$ and $\partial_{\pi} \log f(X_i) = -1/(1 - \hat{\pi})$. The score equation $\partial_{\pi} \ell = 0$ at the MLE gives

$$0 = n_0 \cdot \frac{1 - \hat{g}_0}{\hat{f}_0} - \frac{n_+}{1 - \hat{\pi}}. \quad (18)$$

Multiplying through by $(1 - \hat{\pi})\hat{f}_0$ and rearranging yields $n_0(1 - \hat{g}_0)(1 - \hat{\pi}) = n_+\hat{f}_0$. Substituting $\hat{f}_0 = \hat{\pi} + (1 - \hat{\pi})\hat{g}_0$ and simplifying:

$$\hat{f}_0 = \hat{p}_0, \quad \text{equivalently} \quad \hat{\pi} + (1 - \hat{\pi})\hat{g}_0 = \frac{n_0}{n}. \quad (19)$$

The fitted zero rate equals the empirical zero rate at the interior MLE.

Step 2: score for μ . The NB score in the mean parameterization is $\partial_{\mu} \log g(x; \mu, \phi) = (x - \mu)/[\mu(1 + \mu\phi)]$. At $x = 0$: $\partial_{\mu} \log g(0) = -1/(1 + \mu\phi)$.

For $X_i = 0$,

$$\partial_\mu \log f(0) = \frac{(1 - \hat{\pi})\hat{g}_0}{\hat{f}_0} \cdot \partial_\mu \log g(0; \hat{\mu}, \hat{\phi}) = -\frac{\hat{\rho}_0}{1 + \hat{\mu}\hat{\phi}},$$

where $\hat{\rho}_0 = (1 - \hat{\pi})\hat{g}_0/\hat{f}_0$ is the posterior probability that an observed zero originates from the NB component.

For $X_i > 0$, $\partial_\mu \log f(X_i) = \partial_\mu \log g(X_i) = (X_i - \hat{\mu})/[\hat{\mu}(1 + \hat{\mu}\hat{\phi})]$.

The score equation $\partial_\mu \ell = 0$ gives

$$0 = -\frac{n_0\hat{\rho}_0}{1 + \hat{\mu}\hat{\phi}} + \sum_{i: X_i > 0} \frac{X_i - \hat{\mu}}{\hat{\mu}(1 + \hat{\mu}\hat{\phi})}.$$

Multiplying through by $\hat{\mu}(1 + \hat{\mu}\hat{\phi})$ and noting that $\sum_{i: X_i > 0} X_i = n\bar{X}$ (zeros contribute nothing) and $\sum_{i: X_i > 0} \hat{\mu} = n_+\hat{\mu}$:

$$\hat{\mu}(n_0\hat{\rho}_0 + n_+) = n\bar{X}. \quad (20)$$

Step 3: combine. From (19), $\hat{f}_0 = \hat{\rho}_0 = n_0/n$, and $(1 - \hat{\pi})\hat{g}_0 = \hat{\rho}_0 - \hat{\pi}$. Therefore

$$\hat{\rho}_0 = \frac{(1 - \hat{\pi})\hat{g}_0}{\hat{f}_0} = \frac{\hat{\rho}_0 - \hat{\pi}}{\hat{\rho}_0} = 1 - \frac{\hat{\pi}}{\hat{\rho}_0}.$$

Substituting into (20):

$$\begin{aligned} n\bar{X} &= \hat{\mu}(n_0\hat{\rho}_0 + n_+) \\ &= \hat{\mu} \left(n_0 \cdot \frac{\hat{\rho}_0 - \hat{\pi}}{\hat{\rho}_0} + n_+ \right) \\ &= \hat{\mu} \left(n_0 - \frac{n_0\hat{\pi}}{\hat{\rho}_0} + n_+ \right) \\ &= \hat{\mu}(n - n\hat{\pi}) && \text{(since } n_0/\hat{\rho}_0 = n \text{ and } n_0 + n_+ = n) \\ &= n\hat{\mu}(1 - \hat{\pi}). \end{aligned}$$

Dividing both sides by n gives $(1 - \hat{\pi})\hat{\mu} = \bar{X}$, the cell-total consistency identity.

Boundary cases. The argument requires both (18) and the μ score equation to be *equality* at the MLE, which fails at the parameter boundary. When $\hat{\pi} = 0$ (no zero inflation needed), (18) becomes the inequality $n_0(1 - \hat{g}_0)/\hat{f}_0 \leq n_+/(1 - \hat{\pi})$, and the identity weakens to $\hat{\mu} = \bar{X}/(1 - \hat{\pi}) = \bar{X}$ via the μ score alone (which becomes a single-population NB score). When $\hat{\pi} = 1$ (data are all zeros), $\hat{\mu}$ is unidentified. The $o_p(1)$ remainder in the theorem statement reflects these boundary regimes, which occur with vanishing probability for genes with nonzero true expression and sufficient n . \square

A.4 Bias bound under ERCC-endogenous capture shift

Reframing as misspecification: what the bound is about. Before giving the proof we make explicit the two distinct objects that the bias-bound theorem and its empirical analogues describe. The spike-in oracle is by construction *misspecified*: it estimates per-gene parameters using a dropout function $\pi_{\text{drop}}(\cdot; \phi_{\text{ercc}})$ that was fit on ERCC spike-ins and is then applied to endogenous transcripts whose true dropout is $\pi_{\text{drop}}(\cdot; \phi_{\text{endo}})$ with $\phi_{\text{endo}} \neq \phi_{\text{ercc}}$. In this setting, classical MLE consistency fails: the estimator does not converge to the true endogenous parameter μ_j but to the *pseudo-true value* $\mu_j^*(\Delta\phi)$ at which the Kullback-Leibler divergence from the true endogenous joint distribution

to the working oracle-likelihood family is minimized [White, 1982]. Theorem 6 is a bound on the *asymptotic pseudo-true bias*

$$b_j(\Delta\phi) := \mu_j^*(\Delta\phi) - \mu_j,$$

which is a deterministic functional of the capture-efficiency gap $\Delta\phi = \phi_{\text{ercc}} - \phi_{\text{endo}}$ alone. The bound is linear in $\Delta\phi$ to first order with coefficient $J_{\mu\phi} = -I_{\mu\mu}^{-1}I_{\mu\phi}$, a Fisher-information ratio (or, more precisely, a sandwich-form sensitivity coefficient in the White 1982 framework that here reduces to a Fisher ratio because the score-misspecification expansion is around the true parameter).

What we actually measure in finite samples, by contrast, is the *empirical residual*

$$r_j(\Delta\phi; n) := \hat{\mu}_j(\Delta\phi) - \mu_j = \underbrace{b_j(\Delta\phi)}_{\text{pseudo-true bias}} + \underbrace{[\hat{\mu}_j(\Delta\phi) - \mu_j^*(\Delta\phi)]}_{\text{finite-sample MLE noise}},$$

the sum of (a) the pseudo-true bias that Theorem 6 bounds and (b) the finite-sample MLE deviation around the pseudo-true value. Under the regularity conditions stated below, the second term is $O_p(n^{-1/2})$ and vanishes in the asymptotic limit. The Monte Carlo estimates in table 5 compute averages of $r_j(\Delta\phi; n)$ over replicates and so include both contributions, but the dominant term at $n = 2,000$ cells is the deterministic pseudo-true bias b_j ; the empirical-residual median tracks the first-order linear-in- s prediction of Theorem 6 within 1pp at $s = +1$, with the residual $O(s^2)$ gap accounted for by the explicit second-order Taylor term in the bound. The $O_p(n^{-1/2})$ component is reported separately as the bootstrap SE column.

This distinction matters because the prediction the bound delivers is about an *asymptotic property of the spike-in oracle under misspecification*: even with arbitrarily many cells, the oracle’s estimate will be biased by $J_{\mu\phi}\Delta\phi$ until the spike-in-endogenous capture gap is closed. No amount of additional data shrinks $b_j(\Delta\phi)$; only better calibration of ϕ_{ercc} to ϕ_{endo} does. The finite-sample noise, in contrast, vanishes at $n^{-1/2}$ regardless of the gap. The empirical match between theory and simulation in fig. 5 is therefore evidence that the pseudo-true bias is the right object for predicting oracle behavior as n grows large.

Regularity conditions. The theorem statement and the bias formula (8) appear in section 8. We assume the conditions stated there: dropout follows a parametric family $\pi_{\text{drop}}(\cdot; \phi)$ identifiable on the relevant range, the spike-in MLE recovers ϕ_{ercc} consistently as the spike-in sample size grows, and the per-gene Fisher information block $I_{\mu\mu}$ is non-singular at the true endogenous parameters. These are standard conditions of White [1982, Theorem 3.2] for the existence and uniqueness of the pseudo-true value μ_j^* in a neighborhood of μ_j .

Proof of theorem 6. The proof characterizes the pseudo-true value $\mu_j^*(\Delta\phi)$ defined as the population maximizer of the misspecified oracle-likelihood,

$$\mu_j^*(\Delta\phi) := \arg \max_m \mathbb{E}_{F_{\text{endo}}} [\ell_j(m; \phi_{\text{endo}} + \Delta\phi)],$$

where the expectation is taken under the true endogenous joint distribution F_{endo} (with true dropout ϕ_{endo}) and the working likelihood uses the shifted parameter $\phi_{\text{endo}} + \Delta\phi$. By definition, μ_j^* solves the expected-score equation

$$\mathbb{E}_{F_{\text{endo}}} [\partial_\mu \ell_j(\mu_j^*(\Delta\phi); \phi_{\text{endo}} + \Delta\phi)] = 0. \quad (21)$$

Note this is an equation in the deterministic functional μ_j^* , not the random variable $\hat{\mu}_j$. The MLE $\hat{\mu}_j(\Delta\phi)$ solves the corresponding sample-score equation $\partial_\mu \ell_j(\hat{\mu}_j; \phi_{\text{endo}} + \Delta\phi) = 0$ and, under the

regularity conditions above, satisfies $\hat{\mu}_j(\Delta\phi) = \mu_j^*(\Delta\phi) + O_p(n^{-1/2})$ by the standard sandwich-MLE expansion [White, 1982].

Expand the expected-score (21) around $(\mu_j, \phi_{\text{endo}})$ (the true endogenous parameters, where the expected score is zero by Fisher's identity) to first order in both arguments:

$$\begin{aligned} 0 &= \mathbb{E}_{F_{\text{endo}}}[\partial_\mu \ell_j(\mu_j; \phi_{\text{endo}})] + \mathbb{E}_{F_{\text{endo}}}[\partial_\mu^2 \ell_j(\mu_j; \phi_{\text{endo}})](\mu_j^*(\Delta\phi) - \mu_j) \\ &\quad + \mathbb{E}_{F_{\text{endo}}}[\partial_\mu \partial_\phi \ell_j(\mu_j; \phi_{\text{endo}})] \cdot \Delta\phi + O(\|\mu_j^* - \mu_j\|^2 + \|\Delta\phi\|^2). \end{aligned}$$

The first term vanishes by Fisher's identity (the true endogenous score has expectation zero under F_{endo}). Solve for the pseudo-true bias:

$$\begin{aligned} b_j(\Delta\phi) := \mu_j^*(\Delta\phi) - \mu_j &= -[\mathbb{E}_{F_{\text{endo}}}[\partial_\mu^2 \ell_j]]^{-1} \mathbb{E}_{F_{\text{endo}}}[\partial_\mu \partial_\phi \ell_j] \cdot \Delta\phi \\ &\quad + O(\|\Delta\phi\|^2). \end{aligned}$$

By the standard exponential-family identities $\mathbb{E}_{F_{\text{endo}}}[\partial_\mu^2 \ell_j] = -I_{\mu\mu}$ and $\mathbb{E}_{F_{\text{endo}}}[\partial_\mu \partial_\phi \ell_j] = -I_{\mu\phi}$ (evaluated at the true endogenous parameters), the leading-order pseudo-true bias is

$$\begin{aligned} b_j(\Delta\phi) &= -[-I_{\mu\mu}]^{-1} \cdot [-I_{\mu\phi}] \cdot \Delta\phi + O(\|\Delta\phi\|^2) \\ &= -I_{\mu\mu}^{-1} I_{\mu\phi} \cdot \Delta\phi + O(\|\Delta\phi\|^2) \\ &= J_{\mu\phi} \cdot \Delta\phi + O(\|\Delta\phi\|^2). \end{aligned}$$

Adding the $O_p(n^{-1/2})$ deviation from the sandwich expansion $\hat{\mu}_j(\Delta\phi) = \mu_j^*(\Delta\phi) + O_p(n^{-1/2})$ yields the empirical-residual decomposition

$$\hat{\mu}_j(\Delta\phi) - \mu_j = J_{\mu\phi} \cdot \Delta\phi + O(\|\Delta\phi\|^2) + O_p(n^{-1/2}),$$

which is exactly (8). The $O_p(n^{-1/2})$ term is the finite-sample MLE noise around the pseudo-true value and vanishes as $n \rightarrow \infty$; the $O(\|\Delta\phi\|^2)$ and $J_{\mu\phi} \cdot \Delta\phi$ terms are the deterministic pseudo-true bias and persist regardless of n . The standard MLE-perturbation identity under misspecification is given in van der Vaart [1998, Section 5.4] and White [1982, Theorem 3.2]. \square

Remark 10 (Logit-intercept shift). For logistic-in-log-y dropout $\pi_{\text{drop}}(y; \phi) = \text{logit}^{-1}(\alpha_0 - \alpha_1 \log(y + 1))$ with $\phi = (\alpha_0, \alpha_1)$ and shift $\Delta\phi = (s, 0)$: (8) reduces to

$$\mathbb{E}[\hat{\mu}_j(s) - \mu_j] = J_{\mu\alpha_0}(\theta_j, \phi_{\text{endo}}) \cdot s + O(s^2),$$

which is linear in s to first order. The empirical results in table 5 exhibit this linear regime for $|s| \leq 0.5$; deviations at $|s| > 1$ reflect second-order corrections and saturation of π_{drop} near 0 or 1 in regions of the gene-expression support where the Taylor expansion no longer controls the remainder. The next corollary gives the explicit formula for $J_{\mu\alpha_0}$ when the gene-expression family is NB.

Corollary 11 (Closed-form $J_{\mu\alpha_0}$ for NB plus logistic dropout). *Let $Y \sim \text{NB}(\mu, \phi_{\text{NB}})$ with mean μ and dispersion ϕ_{NB} , so that the score in the mean parameter is $s_y := \partial_\mu \log f(y; \mu, \phi_{\text{NB}}) = (y - \mu)/[\mu(1 + \mu\phi_{\text{NB}})]$. Let $\pi_{\text{drop}}(y; \alpha_0, \alpha_1) = \sigma(\alpha_0 - \alpha_1 \log(y + 1))$ with $\sigma(t) = (1 + e^{-t})^{-1}$. Write $p_y := \pi_{\text{drop}}(y; \alpha_0, \alpha_1)$ and $q_y := 1 - p_y$, and let $f_y := f(y; \mu, \phi_{\text{NB}})$. Define*

$$P_0 := f_0 + \sum_{y \geq 1} f_y p_y, \quad P_x := f_x q_x \text{ for } x \geq 1.$$

The first-derivative scores are

$$\begin{aligned}\psi_\mu(0) &:= \partial_\mu \log P_0 = \frac{f_0 s_0 + \sum_{y \geq 1} f_y p_y s_y}{P_0}, & \psi_\mu(x) &= s_x \text{ for } x \geq 1, \\ \psi_{\alpha_0}(0) &:= \partial_{\alpha_0} \log P_0 = \frac{\sum_{y \geq 1} f_y p_y q_y}{P_0}, & \psi_{\alpha_0}(x) &= -p_x \text{ for } x \geq 1.\end{aligned}$$

The Fisher information blocks at (μ, α_0) are

$$I_{\mu\mu} = \psi_\mu(0)^2 P_0 + \sum_{x \geq 1} s_x^2 f_x q_x, \quad (22)$$

$$I_{\mu\alpha_0} = \psi_\mu(0) \psi_{\alpha_0}(0) P_0 - \sum_{x \geq 1} s_x p_x f_x q_x, \quad (23)$$

and the bias sensitivity coefficient is

$$J_{\mu\alpha_0}(\mu, \phi_{\text{NB}}, \alpha_0, \alpha_1) = -\frac{I_{\mu\alpha_0}}{I_{\mu\mu}}. \quad (24)$$

Proof of corollary 11. The score expressions ψ_μ and ψ_{α_0} follow by direct differentiation of $\log P_0$ and $\log P_x$, using $\partial_\mu f_y = f_y s_y$ for the NB density and $\partial_{\alpha_0} p_y = p_y q_y$ for the logistic. The Fisher information identities $I_{\mu\mu} = \mathbb{E}[\psi_\mu(X)^2]$ and $I_{\mu\alpha_0} = \mathbb{E}[\psi_\mu(X) \psi_{\alpha_0}(X)]$ then yield (22)–(23) on substituting $\mathbb{E}[\cdot] = \psi_\mu(0) \psi_{\alpha_0}(0) P_0 + \sum_{x \geq 1} \psi_\mu(x) \psi_{\alpha_0}(x) P_x$ and using $\psi_\mu(x) = s_x$, $\psi_{\alpha_0}(x) = -p_x$ for $x \geq 1$. The bias coefficient (24) is then the general formula $J_{\mu\phi} = -I_{\mu\mu}^{-1} I_{\mu\phi}$ specialized to the present setting. \square

Remark 12 (Numerical evaluation). The expressions in (22) and (23) involve infinite sums over the NB support, which converge geometrically and can be truncated at y_{max} chosen so that $\mathbb{P}\{Y > y_{\text{max}}\} < \epsilon$ for any desired ϵ . An R implementation evaluating (24) for a grid of $(\mu, \alpha_0, \alpha_1)$ values is in `scripts/compute_J_theoretical.R`. The first-order prediction $\mathbb{E}[\hat{\mu}_j(s) - \mu_j] \approx J_{\mu\alpha_0} s$ can then be compared to the empirical bias from table 5; the comparison is shown in fig. 5.

Remark 13 (Connection to the useful zone). The useful zone $|s| \leq 0.5$ in section 8 is the regime in which the first-order term in (8) dominates and oracle bias remains smaller than naive bias. Outside this regime, the second-order term and any model misspecification in π_{drop} 's parametric family produce bias comparable to or larger than naive, yielding the empirical crossover observed in fig. 4.

B Simulation details

All simulations use a Poisson–Beta two-state expression model [Kim and Marioni, 2013]: per cell, an active-promoter probability is drawn from $\text{Beta}(a, b)$, then count drawn from $\text{Poisson}(\lambda \cdot p_{\text{active}})$. Setting $a = 0.5$ and $\lambda = \mu \cdot \text{burst_factor}$ with $\text{burst_factor} = 5$ gives mean expression μ and realistic bursty dynamics.

Genes are drawn from a log-normal μ distribution ($\log\text{mean} = 0.5$, $\log\text{sd} = 1.3$) unless otherwise stated. ERCC concentrations span log-uniform $[0.5, 50]$ across 92 transcripts.

The naive ZINB and oracle estimators are implemented in ~ 200 lines of R. The full simulation library, version drivers (`run.v1.R–run.v9`), per-replicate result files, and per-version write-ups are available in the `scrna-coarsening-sims` repository at <https://github.com/queelius/scrna-coarsening-sims>; see the Code availability section for details.

C Code availability

The R code implementing the methodology and reproducing all simulation and analysis results is available in the `scrna-coarsening-sims` repository at <https://github.com/queelius/scrna-coarsening-sims>. This includes the naive ZINB and oracle estimators, the version drivers (`run_v1.R`–`run_v9`), the analysis scripts (`compute_implied_shift.R`, `compute_J_theoretical.R`, `compute_table_uncertainties.R`, `make_figures.R`, `run_v9_method_comparison.R`), and the cached per-replicate result files needed to regenerate every table and figure. A versioned archive of the repository will be deposited on Zenodo and the resulting DOI assigned on deposit; the DOI is not yet minted at the time of writing. The Tabula Muris analysis pipeline (section 9) is in `run_v8_tabula_muris.R`; it requires the spleen counts file from figshare (DOI 10.6084/m9.figshare.5715040) and the ERCC concentration table from Thermo Fisher (`cms_095046.txt`).